

INTEGRATE-LMEDC

Outcomes of the Gap Analysis of Large Medical Cohorts

Work Package 3 – Deliverable 3.1

Project name	INTEGRATE-LMedC
Project acronym	INTEGRATE-LMedC
Project number	101131809
Deliverable no	3.1
Deliverable title	Outcomes of the gap analysis of large medical cohorts
Contractual delivery month	M12 – December 2024
Responsible partner	FSJD-CERCA
Author(s)	Lydia-Hanaa Faris (FSJD), Francina Mesquida Veny (FSJD)
Other contributors	Josep Maria Haro (FSJD), Kurt Majcen (BBMRI-ERIC), Andreas Tuerk (BBMRI-ERIC), Rogier van der Stijl (UMCG), Kristian Hveem (NTNU)
Dissemination level	PU – Public
Description of deliverable	Results of the gap analysis to guide future decision-making research efforts for the development of next-generation RI (research infrastructure)

TABLE OF CONTENTS

DOCUMENT INFORMATION	5
DOCUMENT HISTORY	5
GLOSSARY	5
1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
2. INTRODUCTION	8
3. DEFINING LARGE MEDICAL COHORTS	10
3.1. PROCESS.....	10
3.2. DEFINITION.....	11
4. IDENTIFICATION OF AREAS OF UNMET MEDICAL NEEDS AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR IMPROVED MEDICAL CARE	12
4.1. DELPHI STUDY.....	12
4.1.1. WHAT IS A DELPHI STUDY?	12
4.1.2. PURPOSE OF THE DELPHI STUDY	12
4.1.3. STUDY DESIGN	13
4.1.4. EXPERT RECRUITMENT.....	15
4.2. EXPERTS INFORMATION	17
4.2.1. PARTICIPANTS BY GENDER.....	17
4.2.2. PARTICIPANTS BY AGE GROUP	17
4.2.3. PARTICIPANTS BY FIELD OF WORK.....	18
4.2.4. PARTICIPANTS BY YEAR OF EXPERIENCE IN THEIR RESPECTIVE FIELDS	18
4.2.5. COUNTRIES IN WHICH EXPERTS WORK.....	19

4.3. DELPHI RESULTS ROUND 120

4.3.1. DISEASES LISTED BY THE EXPERTS21

4.3.1.1. TREATMENT EFFICACY:25

4.3.1.2. TREATMENT ACCESSIBILITY:28

4.3.1.3. EXISTENCE OF PREVENTION STRATEGIES:30

4.3.1.4. NEED FOR LARGE MEDICAL COHORTS:33

4.3.1.5. NEED FOR POPULATION COHORTS:36

4.3.1.6. NEED FOR CLINICAL COHORTS:39

4.3.2. DISEASES SELECTED BY EXPERTS FROM PRE-DEFINED LIST OF DISEASES (DALYs 2021)43

4.3.2.1. TREATMENT EFFICACY:44

4.3.2.2. TREATMENT ACCESSIBILITY:47

4.3.2.3. EXISTENCE OF PREVENTION STRATEGIES:50

4.3.2.4. NEED FOR LARGE MEDICAL COHORTS:53

4.3.2.5. NEED FOR POPULATION COHORTS:56

4.3.2.6. NEED FOR CLINICAL COHORTS:59

4.4. RESULTS ROUND 262

4.4.1.1. TREATMENT EFFICACY:63

4.4.1.2. TREATMENT ACCESSIBILITY:65

4.4.1.3. EXISTENCE OF PREVENTION STRATEGIES:68

4.4.1.4. NEED FOR LARGE MEDICAL COHORTS:70

4.4.1.5. NEED FOR POPULATION COHORTS:73

4.4.1.6. NEED FOR CLINICAL COHORTS:76

4.5. NOMINAL INTERVIEWS82

4.5.1. WHAT ARE NOMINAL INTERVIEWS82

4.5.2. OBJECTIVE82

4.5.3. RECRUITMENT PROCESS83

4.5.4. INTERVIEW PROCESS83

4.5.5. FINDINGS84

4.5.5.1. DISEASE AREAS WITH UNMET MEDICAL NEEDS: FINAL SELECTION FOR MAPPING84

5. MAPPING OF LARGE MEDICAL COHORTS86

5.1. SCOPING REVIEW86

5.2. OBJECTIVE.....86

5.3. METHODOLOGY87

5.3.1. RESEARCH DESIGN AND REVIEW QUESTION87

5.3.2. SEARCH STRATEGY METHODS87

5.3.3. ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA87

5.3.4. MANUSCRIPT SELECTION91

5.3.4.1. ABSTRACT REVIEW91

5.3.4.2. FULL-TEXT REVIEW.....91

5.3.5. DATA EXTRACTION AND COHORT IDENTIFICATION92

5.4. FINAL MAPPING RESULTS98

5.4.1. DEPRESSION RESULTS98

5.4.2. AD AND OTHER DEMENTIAS RESULTS106

5.4.3. ENDOMETRIOSIS RESULTS111

6. GUIDANCE ON NEEDS OF LMEDC TO BE SUPPORTED BY A RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE114

6.1. OBJECTIVE.....114

6.2. DELPHI STUDY114

6.3. NOMINAL INTERVIEWS.....114

6.4. KEY CHALLENGES AND NEEDS115

6.4.1. DATA SCOPE AND REPRESENTATIVITY 115

6.4.2. DATA QUALITY AND STRUCTURE 116

6.4.3. DATA ACCESS AND SHARING 116

6.4.4. METHODOLOGICAL AND OPERATIONAL CHALLENGES..... 117

6.5. RECOMMENDATIONS118

6.5.1. DATA SCOPE AND REPRESENTATIVITY & DATA QUALITY AND STRUCTURE: 118

6.5.2. DATA ACCESS AND SHARING: 118

6.5.3. METHODOLOGICAL AND OPERATIONAL CHALLENGES:..... 119

6.5.4. TRANSVERSAL MATTERS:..... 119

7. DISCUSSION..... 121

7.1. KEY FINDINGS121

7.1.1. IMPLICATIONS OF THE FINDINGS..... ¡ERROR! MARCADOR NO DEFINIDO.

7.2. STRENGTHS AND LIMITATIONS126

8. REFERENCES..... 128

9. APPENDICES 130

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Document history

Date	Version	Editor	Change	Status
19-12-2024	0.1	Lydia-Hanaa Faris, Francina Mesquida Veny	Initial draft	Complete
28-12-2024	1.0	Lydia-Hanaa Faris, Francina Mesquida Veny	Revised draft including comments by internal review and approved by Scientific Coordinator	Complete
22-01-2025	1.0	NA	Version approved by Scientific Coordinator	Complete

Glossary

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
BBMRI-ERIC	Biobanking and BioMolecular resources Research Infrastructure – European Research Infrastructure Consortium
AD	Alzheimer's disease
DALYs	Disability-adjusted life years
DLB	Dementia with Lewy bodies
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
ECRIN	European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network

FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
FSJD	Fundació Privada per a la Recerca i la Docència Sant Joan de Déu
FTD	Frontotemporal dementia
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IRB	Institution Review Board
LMedC	Large Medical Cohorts
MCI	Mild cognitive impairment
Mu	Masarykova Universita
NTNU	Norges Teknisk-Naturvitenskapelige Universitet
PCC	Population, Concept, and Context
PD	Parkinson's disease
QI.LAB.MED	QI.LAB.MED SPIN-OFF of Padova University
RI	Research Infrastructure
SCD	Subjective cognitive decline
UMCG	University Medical Center Groningen
VaD	Vascular dementia
WP	Work Package

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The WP3 of the INTEGRATE-LMedC consortium is part of the first phase of the project, which intends to establish an overview of the current landscape regarding large medical cohorts (LMedC) and research infrastructures (RI) in Europe. The main objectives of this WP were: 1) to conduct a gap analysis of unmet medical needs, 2) to map related existing LMedC in Europe and 3) to provide guidance to support the development of a research infrastructure concept. Before these objectives could be addressed, a formal definition of LMedC was established, to be used throughout all current work. The definition set a threshold for “large” and delimited the concepts of “medical” and “cohort”.

For the gap analysis (objective 1), a two-round Delphi study was conducted with different stakeholder experts in the field. Questions in the Delphi study allowed to identify clinical areas with insufficient data in Europe. Subsequent nominal interviews allowed to reach a final consensus on the representative areas decided by the experts: depression, Alzheimer’s disease and other dementias and endometriosis.

To continue with the following objective of the WP3, a scoping review was conducted to map existing LMedC in Europe (objective 2) for the selected areas of unmet medical needs. From the 1431, 243 and 105 results from the initial search (for depression, AD and other dementias and endometriosis, respectively), a total of 48, 16 and 1 LMedC were identified. The low number of identified cohorts reinforces the idea that selected disorders represent areas of unmet medical needs.

Finally, experts consulted during the gap analysis were also asked to comment on current barriers and propose recommendations, to provide guidance for a research infrastructure (objective 3). Received feedback identified lack of data quality and comparability, as well as reluctance to share data as the main limitations, and confirmed that the generation of a research infrastructure could help to approach them.

2. INTRODUCTION

The INTEGRATE-LMedC consortium is developing a new next-generation research infrastructure (RI) concept for Large Medical Cohorts (LMedC) to assist and guide decision-makers. The aim of this RI is to facilitate the use and the standardization of large medical cohorts in order to promote science and medical advancements not only in Europe but on a global level. The project brings together 11 interdisciplinary partners, including established ERIC / ESFRI infrastructures like BBMRI-ERIC, ECRIN, EIRENE and EBRAINS, all of which have considerable experience in the design and implementation of European RIs. In the first phase, the consortium will establish an overview of the current landscape regarding LMedC and RI to detect any missing components such as cohort data and samples, tools, services, quality standards, governance structures and other impediments to effective RI use, including ethical and legal ones.

Large medical cohorts play an essential role in understanding and solving public health problems, as well as clinical diseases (communicable and non-communicable diseases). These cohorts enable the collection of large-scale data and samples on diverse populations, offering opportunities to identify risk factors, track disease trajectories and assess the impact of medical interventions and health policies. However, the effective use of data and samples from these cohorts remains a major challenge, due to limitations in data access, lack of harmonization of methodologies and complex ethical and legal frameworks.

In medical research, LMedC are perhaps the only resources providing such extensive qualitative longitudinal datasets. Looking at the European context, the landscape of LMedC is a good starting point as it encapsulates a number of studies, which are aimed at explaining cause, treatment and trends related to population health. However, despite their strong potential, LMedC face several barriers that reduce their effectiveness and impact.

Faced with these challenges, INTEGRATE-LMedC WP3 has used different methods to identify strategic priorities and gaps in the LMedC landscape to support further development of the RI concept. To ensure the success of this project, WP3's main objectives are to

conduct a gap analysis of the European landscape of large medical cohorts, to identify unmet medical needs and opportunities for improving medical care and finally to guide a more effective decision-making and research efforts and support the development of a next-generation RI to streamline the use of cohort data and samples, now and in the future.

This initiative grouped interdisciplinary experts who collaborated to adopt a comprehensive approach that addressed the diverse needs of the research community. To consider the perspectives of all social groups, WP3 engaged different stakeholders, such as patient advocacy groups and experts in the humanities and social sciences. The work culminated in the development of a detailed structure with measurable finds and objectives, which formed the basis for the gap analysis and cohort mapping.

The gap analysis was the basis for the formulation of strategic orientations. WP3 relied on a combination of the Delphi method and nominal interviews with experts and key stakeholders. These approaches helped consolidate a consensus among experts and stakeholders, defining recommendations for the development of next-generation RI. This consensus enabled the selection of three representative areas decided by the experts, based on modified prioritization criteria to carry out a mapping on the areas.

Finally, regarding the mapping of LMedC, a scoping review was carried out to identify relevant medical and population cohorts of the last five years (2019-2024). This effort focused on mapping cohorts related to depression, endometriosis and Alzheimer's disease and other dementias. The analysis yielded detailed data on the cohorts, their target populations, data collection methods and follow-up, and other characteristics essential for the understanding of the existing cohorts.

Figure 1 illustrates the general outline of WP3.

Figure 1 – General Outline of WP3

3. DEFINING LARGE MEDICAL COHORTS

3.1. Process

As part of the INTEGRATE-LMedC project, the first step of WP3 was to define large medical cohorts.

The definition of large medical cohorts involved a methodological approach to ensure that the data are relevant and provide scope for project tasks, without limiting a priori directions for concept development. It is worth noting that the current definition is a working definition adopted at the start of the project. Input gathered during the project and feedback from experts/stakeholders can influence the working definition¹ towards a definitive definition in the final RI concept plan at the end of project.

The first step was the determination of the population threshold for a cohort to be considered “large”. This decision involved choosing between cohorts representing a large percentage of the target population or an absolute cutoff number. An absolute numerical threshold was selected; of 1000 for clinical cohorts, 10000 for population cohorts, and 0,5-1% of a country’s total disease population for rare disease cohorts.

The second step was to define “medical”; in this part, it was decided that not only clinical cohorts would be included, but also population cohorts, as they also answer health-related questions, providing a broad scope. In short, all cohorts that collect health-related data for health research can be considered medical cohorts.

¹ A working definition is a temporary, practical explanation or interpretation of a term, concept or idea, established for a specific purpose or context. It is not necessarily a definitive or universally agreed definition, but it is a useful guide to discussion, analysis or action in a given context.

Finally, the definition of “cohort” was based on the setting of a broad but defined research purpose, excluding direct secondary use of data collected in primary care processes, as well as the setting of cohorts that include clinical data through electronic medical records retrospectively. Clinical trials were also excluded from this definition as they generally have a “closed” research objective, where data are collected to answer a specific question. Cohorts, on the other hand, are considered “open” as they collect data and samples to answer a wide range of current and future research questions in a certain field. In addition, there is already a research infrastructure (RI) for clinical trials, namely ECRIN, which focuses on supporting the collection and management of clinical trial data.

3.2. Definition

A medical cohort refers to a group of individuals with a shared condition, characteristic or exposure who might be followed over time to collect extensive health-related data and/or biological materials for current and future health research. The data and biological materials collected from a medical cohort are stored as databank and/or biobank collections. In this project, we neither consider interventional clinical trials nor databanks based on health registries without specific follow-up as medical cohorts. We consider a medical cohort as “large” in the following circumstances:

- A clinical cohort (observational) comprising over 1000 participants selected for a health condition; or
- A rare disease cohort comprising over 0,5-1% (as a rough guideline) of the total disease population of the country; or
- A population cohort comprising over 10000 participants.

4. IDENTIFICATION OF AREAS OF UNMET MEDICAL NEEDS AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR IMPROVED MEDICAL CARE

4.1. Delphi study

4.1.1. What is a Delphi study?

The Delphi method seeks to obtain consensus on the opinions of experts, termed panel members, through a series of structured questionnaires. As part of the process, the responses from each round are analysed and summarized to proceed to the following round. The Delphi method is therefore an iterative multi-stage process designed to combine opinion into group consensus. It is useful in areas where observational evidence is either limited or inconclusive, as it allows experts to provide informed input. Through anonymizing participants and providing structure to the process, the Delphi method ensures that the consensus is built on reflective collective experience and not determined by the most influential opinions.

4.1.2. Purpose of the Delphi study

The goal of the Delphi study was to narrow down gaps in the cohort landscape and identify areas of medical needs that are not adequately provided in Europe. By engaging in several rounds of structured feedback and consensus along with decision making, the Delphi method allowed the project to provide guidance for decision-making and research prioritization in the European landscape of LMedC.

One of the first steps in the WP3 is to identify areas of unmet medical need that could potentially benefit from research arising from large medical and population cohorts. By identifying areas lacking adequate cohort studies, the prioritization of the allocation of resources and attention to these domains could be strengthened.

Stimulating cohort studies in fields with high unmet medical need will provide the opportunity to:

- Allow the observation of a group of people over an extended period, leading to a better understanding of how diseases develop, progress and interact with different factors over time.
- Establish correlations and if possible causal relationships between exposures and outcomes, meaning that by following individuals before the development of a condition/disease, tracking their exposure could help determine if there is a cause-effect relationship.
- Provide valuable insights that can potentially be used to improve treatment outcomes, particularly regarding safety.

The main objective of this study is to decide on the disease areas with unmet medical needs in Europe that could benefit from large medical cohorts, assessing different important factors for each disease:

- Treatment effectiveness;
- Treatment accessibility;
- Prevention strategies;
- Need of large medical cohort data (population and clinical cohorts).

4.1.3. Study Design

In the current study, a modified version of the Delphi technique was applied consisting of 2 rounds. As opposed to a classical Delphi study, the first round did not consist of a complete open questionnaire to obtain all qualitative input. Instead, half of the questionnaire was designed with open-ended questions, while the other half included a **pre-established list of diseases** defined by their contribution to Disability-Adjusted Life Years (DALYs). The DALYs 2021 Level 3 classification, which focuses on the specific diseases instead of groups of diseases, was utilized. The 20 diseases with the greatest impact in terms of disease burden (DALYs) in the regions of Eastern, Central and Western Europe were identified to

guide experts in their assessment of unmet medical needs. (Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation, 2024). Included questions can be found in **Appendixes A and B**. In the second round, the 15 most listed/selected diseases have been displayed, of which experts had to select 3 that they consider have a lack of research data, leading to unaddressed medical demands.

Figure 2 illustrates the general outline of the current Delphi study.

The Delphi study was a multi-center, international initiative across Europe, with an exploratory observational design. It was approved by the ethics committee (CEIM Fundació Sant Joan de Déu). All participants signed informed consent forms to ensure that they fully understood the purpose of the study and agreed to participate voluntarily. This process ensured ethical standards, protected participants’ rights and guaranteed compliance with current regulations.

Figure 2 – General Outline Delphi procedure

All survey rounds were administered using **Qualtrics software** (Qualtrics, Provo, UT). Qualtrics is a web application designed for creating surveys with response formats, various distribution methods, and data management capabilities. The software adheres to the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and is compliant with regulations pertaining to the processing and storage of protected information.

4.1.4. Expert Recruitment

The objective of the Delphi study was to obtain the participation of 80-100 experts. To this end, a desk search was conducted to identify experts in a variety of fields, including physicians, citizen or patient associations, health professionals practicing primary care, health policy or political decision-makers, public health professionals, health care managers, clinical researchers, epidemiological or public health researchers, translational researchers and cohort researchers.

In addition, the INTEGRATE-LMedC consortium was asked to suggest names of experts they knew of whom that could be approached. To expand the reach, a call to potential participants via one of BBMRI-ERIC's e-mail lists was put out. The experts, who had accepted our invitation to participate, were further encouraged to suggest other potential experts who might be interested in the study. This approach (**Figure 3**) enabled the involvement of a diverse group of experts working across Europe.

Figure 3 – Delphi Experts Participati

4.2. Experts Information

The demographic and professional characteristics of the experts who contributed to the study provide a better understanding of the respondents' profiles and expertise. The exploration of the distribution of participants is based on gender, age range, profession, country in which they are professionally active and years of experience in the selected field.

4.2.1. Participants by gender

4.2.2. Participants by age group

4.2.3. Participants by field of work

4.2.4. Participants by year of experience in their respective fields

4.2.5. Countries in which experts work

The 22 countries in which the experts who participated to the study work are the following:

4.3. Delphi Results Round 1

The first round of this Delphi study was to determine the initial disease areas experts believe have a deficiency in available research data in Europe, further contributing to unmet medical needs. The questionnaire was divided into two parts:

As part of the first round of our Delphi study, experts were asked to identify diseases that they perceived to have a lack of data from cohort studies, leading to unfulfilled medical demands. To do this, participants were asked **to list up to three diseases** according to

their expertise. Each disease identified was then assessed using a five-point Likert scale, through a series of statements, covering various aspects such as treatment effectiveness, treatment accessibility, prevention strategies, the need for clinical and population cohort data.

In the second part of the questionnaire, the experts were asked **to select three diseases from a pre-established list of diseases (DALYs)**. For each of the selected diseases, the participants then answered the same series of questions as in Round 1, using a five-point Likert scale.

This combined approach enabled us to explore both spontaneous perceptions and priorities guided by global public health data (DALYs).

4.3.1. Diseases listed by the experts

The table below (**Table 1**) shows the diseases identified by the experts during the first round of the Delphi study. Each expert was asked to list up to three diseases that they considered to have a lack of data from cohort studies, leading to unmet medical needs. The frequency shown represents the number of times each disease was mentioned by the participants.

Please list the three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in available research data, contributing to unmet medical needs in Europe?

Disease	Frequency
Mental disorders	9
Alzheimer's/Dementia (incl. neurodegenerative diseases)	7
Endometriosis	4
Rare diseases (incl. rare genetic diseases and rare cancers)	3
Pancreatic Cancer	3
Diabetes	3

Cardiovascular diseases (CVD)	3
Hypertension	2
Cystic fibrosis	2
Metabolic syndrome	2
Hearing loss	2
Cancer	2
Stroke	2
Antibiotic resistances	2
Spinal cord injury	1
Poverty, disorders related to low social status	1
COVID	1
Pediatric post-COVID syndrome	1
Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS)	1
ADHD (in adults)	1
Multiple sclerosis	1
Primary ciliary dyskinesia	1
Atherosclerosis	1
Musculoskeletal disorders	1
Cognitive / motor disabilities	1
Asthma	1
Fabry disease	1
Schizophrenia	1
Child abuse	1

Irritable bowel syndrome (IBS)	1
Obesity	1
Mitochondrial diseases	1
Autism spectrum disorders	1
Low back pain	1
Minen (multiple independent neuroendocrine neoplasms)	1
Repeated influenza/respiratory infections	1
Duchenne muscular dystrophy	1
Cardioencephalomyopathy	1
Huntington disease	1
Metabolic disorders	1
Fibromyalgia	1
Ovarian cancer	1
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD)	1
Migraine	1
Immunosuppression in Organ Transplantation	1
Pseudoxanthoma elasticum	1
Eating disorders	1
Mast cell activation syndrome (MCAS)	1
Premenstrual dysphoric disorder	1
Metabolic-associated fatty liver disease	1
Rett's disease	1
Pediatric cardiovascular diseases	1

Traumatic brain injury	1
Dental conditions	1
Tobacco and vaping environmental impact	1
Soft tissue sarcoma	1
Vision deficiency	1
Sleep Disorders (e.g., Insomnia)	1
Lower leg amputation	1
Neurodermatitis	1
Glioma	1
Chronic fatigue syndrome	1
Prematurity	1
Chronic inflammation	1
Cerebral infarction (i63-i64)	1
Atopic dermatitis	1
Respiratory diseases	1
Bronchiectasis	1
Atopic diseases due to immune defects	1
Acute diverticulitis	1
Sickle cell disease	1
Pregnancy & offspring following bariatric surgery	1
Food intolerances	1
Early infant death syndrome	1
Pediatric rare tumors	1

Neonatal hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy	1
Alcohol-Attributable Deaths Due to Self-Harm & Suicide	1

Table 1 – Diseases listed by the experts that they believe have a deficiency in available research data, contributing to unmet medical needs in Europe

The most listed diseases are **mental disorders, Alzheimer’s disease and other dementias, rare diseases, endometriosis and pancreatic cancer.**

The results obtained from the experts' Likert-scale assessments are used to analyse various aspects of unmet medical needs for each disease identified. Shown analyses cover dimensions of the **5 most listed** diseases such as the **availability and accessibility of effective treatments**, the existence of **prevention strategies**, and the need for **large medical (clinical) and population cohorts.**

4.3.1.1. Treatment efficacy:

The following graphs present the experts' assessment of the perceived efficacy of available treatments for the various diseases identified:

The results show a division among experts regarding the availability of treatments regarding mental disorders. 44% of experts considered mental disorder treatments to be accessible,

while 44% express a neutral position. However, 11% expressed a strongly negative opinion, underlining the absence of a clear consensus.

Most experts were critical of treatment effectiveness for Alzheimer’s disease (AD), with 50% expressing strong disagreement and 25% disagreement. Only 13% of participants thought treatments were effective (agree), while 13% took a neutral stance (neither agree nor disagree). These results indicate an overall negative perception of treatment efficacy.

A large majority of experts (75%) considered that the treatments for rare diseases were not effective, expressing a strong disagreement (strongly disagree). 25% of participants adopted a neutral position (neither agree nor disagree), while no expert expressed a positive

opinion on the efficacy of treatments (agree or strongly agree). These results highlight an overall negative perception.

Experts were divided on the availability of effective treatments for endometriosis, with 50% neither agreeing nor disagreeing. However, 25% disagreed and 25% strongly disagreed. These results reflect an overall negative perception.

Most of the experts (67%) considered the availability of treatments for pancreatic cancer to be highly effective (strongly agree), while 33% considered it to be moderately effective (agree). No participant expressed a neutral or negative opinion, reflecting a generally favourable consensus on this point.

4.3.1.2. Treatment accessibility:

The following graphs summarize experts' opinions on the accessibility of current treatments for each disease:

Most experts (44%) considered the accessibility of treatments for mental disorders to be insufficient (disagree), and 22% express strong disagreement (strongly disagree). On the other hand, 22% of participants who chose this disease consider treatments to be accessible (agree), while 11% adopt a neutral position (neither agree nor disagree). These results reveal a predominantly negative perception, with divergent opinions on this point.

63% of experts considered treatment accessibility to be very satisfactory (strongly agree) for Alzheimer’s disease and other dementias. However, 25% expressed strong dissatisfaction (strongly disagree) and 13% took a neutral position (neither agree nor disagree).

While the majority of experts (75%) disagreed about treatment accessibility (disagree), 25% expressed strong disagreement (strongly disagree). No participant expressed a positive or neutral opinion on this subject, indicating a largely negative perception of treatment accessibility.

The results show a mixed distribution of opinions among the experts. For 25% of participants, treatment accessibility was considered highly satisfactory (strongly agree), while 50% adopted a neutral stance (neither agree nor disagree). The remaining 25% of experts strongly disagreed.

The results reveal an unfavourable perception of treatment accessibility overall, with 67% of experts expressing moderate disagreement and 33% strong disagreement. No participant expressed a positive or neutral opinion, highlighting major concerns about access to treatment.

4.3.1.3. Existence of prevention strategies:

The following graphs summarize experts' perceptions of the existence and effectiveness of prevention strategies for the diseases identified:

Most experts (44%) considered that effective prevention strategies exist for mental disorders, while 33% express moderate disagreement (disagree) and 11% strong disagreement (strongly disagree). A further 11% took a neutral stance (neither agree nor disagree). These results suggest a generally favourable opinion, although there are still significant differences of opinion regarding the effectiveness of existing prevention strategies.

Regarding Alzheimer’s disease and other dementias, 38% of participants adopted a neutral position (neither agree nor disagree), while 25% expressed moderate disagreement

(disagree) and 38% strong disagreement (strongly disagree). No expert expressed a positive opinion, reflecting significant concerns about existing prevention strategies for AD.

The results show a predominantly negative perception of treatment and prevention strategies for rare diseases. 50% of experts expressed strong disagreement, and 25% moderate disagreement. A smaller proportion (25%) adopt a neutral position (neither agree nor disagree), with no positive views on the effectiveness of existing strategies to prevent rare diseases.

The results suggest a majority of negative responses concerning endometriosis prevention strategies. 50% of experts expressed moderate disagreement (disagree), while 25% expressed strong disagreement (strongly disagree). However, 25% agreed on the existence of effective strategies.

According to the table, 67% of experts expressed strong disagreement, while 33% expressed moderate disagreement for the existence of proven strategies to prevent pancreatic cancer. No expert expressed a positive or neutral opinion, underlining major concerns about the existence of preventative strategies for pancreatic cancer.

4.3.1.4. Need for large medical cohorts:

The following graphs show experts' assessments of the need for large medical cohorts to fill data gaps:

The majority of experts (88%) felt the necessity of large medical cohorts to support treatment and prevention of mental disorders, with 44% expressing strong agreement (strongly agree) and 44% moderate agreement (agree). 11% of experts remained neutral (neither agree nor disagree), while no one expressed a negative opinion. These results indicate a clear consensus on the importance of large medical cohorts to improve treatment and prevention strategies.

For Alzheimer's disease and other dementias, the results show total consensus among experts on the need for large medical cohorts to support treatment and prevention strategies. 50% of experts expressed strong agreement and 50% moderate agreement.

All experts (100%) agree on the importance of large medical cohorts to enhance treatment and prevention strategies for rare diseases. With 25% of experts expressing strong agreement and 75% moderate agreement.

Similarly to Alzheimer’s disease and rare diseases, all experts (100%) agree on the importance of large medical cohorts to enhance treatment and prevention strategies for endometriosis.

All experts recognize the importance of large medical cohorts to support treatment and prevention strategies for pancreatic cancer. In fact, 67% of participants expressed strong agreement and 33% moderate agreement.

4.3.1.5. Need for population cohorts:

The results concerning the need for population cohorts to better understand the impact of diseases are presented in the following graphs:

There is a strong consensus among experts on the need for population cohort studies to improve the treatment and prevention of mental illness. Indeed, 44% of experts strongly agree and 56% agree, with no neutral or negative opinions expressed. These results show unanimous support for the importance of population cohorts in improving mental health strategies.

Most experts agree that population cohort studies could enhance/improve the treatment and prevention of Alzheimer's disease. Indeed, 50% of experts strongly agree and 38% agree.

However, 13% expressed moderate disagreement. These results indicate a broad consensus in favour of population cohorts for this disease.

All experts (100%) agreed on the need for population cohort studies to enhance/improve the treatment and prevention of rare diseases.

Concerning the use of population cohort studies to improve prevention and treatment of endometriosis, 50% of experts strongly agreed, 25% agreed and 25% neither agreed nor disagreed.

All experts agree on the need for population cohort studies to improve the treatment and prevention of pancreatic cancer. 67% of experts strongly agreed and 33% agreed.

4.3.1.6. Need for clinical cohorts:

The results concerning the need for clinical cohorts to better understand the impact of diseases are presented in the following graphs:

Most experts (78%) supported the need for clinical cohorts to enhance/improve the treatment and prevention of mental illness, with 11% expressing strong agreement (strongly agree) and 67% moderate agreement (agree). 22% of experts adopted a neutral position.

Regarding Alzheimer's disease and other dementias, most experts (88%) recognized the need for clinical cohorts to improve the treatment and prevention of mental illness, with 38% expressing strong agreement and 50% moderate agreement. However, 13% of experts expressed moderate disagreement.

All experts (100%) agreed on the need for clinical cohorts to improve the treatment and prevention of rare diseases. 25% of experts strongly agreed and 75% agreed. No expert expressed a neutral or negative opinion, indicating unanimous support for the importance of clinical cohorts in this field.

All experts (100%) agreed on the need for clinical cohorts to improve the treatment and prevention of endometriosis.

All experts (100%) agreed on the need for clinical cohorts to improve the treatment and prevention of endometriosis. 67% of experts strongly agreed with the need of clinical cohorts to enhance and improve treatment and prevention of endometriosis, and 33% agreed.

4.3.2. Diseases selected by experts from pre-defined list of diseases (DALYs 2021)

The table below (**Table 2**) shows the diseases selected by the experts from the pre-defined DALY-based list during the first round of the Delphi study. Each expert was asked to select up to three diseases that they considered to have a lack of data from cohort studies, leading to unmet medical needs. The frequency shown represents the number of times each disease was selected by the participants.

Disease	Frequency
Depressive Disorders	22
Alzheimer's disease and other dementias	16
Low back pain	14
Falls	11
Headache disorders	11
Pancreatic cancer	10
Age-related and other hearing loss	7
Stroke	5
Diabetes mellitus	5
Ischemic heart disease	4
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	4
Oral disorders	3
Hypertensive heart disorder	3
Tracheal, bronchus and lung cancer	2

Colon and rectum cancer	2
Cirrhosis and other chronic liver diseases	2
Chronic kidney disease	2
Breast cancer	1
Cardiomyopathy and myocarditis	0

Table 2 – Diseases listed by the experts from the pre-defined DALY-based list.

The most selected diseases are **depressive disorders, Alzheimer’s disease and other dementias, low back pain, falls and headache disorders.**

The results obtained from the experts' Likert-scale assessments are used to analyse various aspects of unmet medical needs for each disease identified. Shown analyses cover dimensions of the **5 most selected** diseases such as the **availability** and **accessibility of effective treatments**, the existence of **prevention strategies**, and the need for **large medical (clinical) and population cohorts.**

4.3.2.1. Treatment efficacy:

The following graphs present the experts' assessment of the perceived efficacy of available treatments for the various diseases identified

Responses regarding depressive disorders' effective treatments availability are widely divided, with 45% of experts agreeing (36% strongly agree, 9% agree). However, 32% of experts remained neutral (neither agree nor disagree) and 23% of experts disagree with the statement expressing that there are effective treatments available for depressive disorders.

88% of the experts who selected AD and other dementias as a disease area with unmet medical needs disagree (44%) or strongly disagree (44%) with the statement. 6% of experts believe that effective treatments are available (agree), while 6% took a neutral stance (neither agree nor disagree). These results indicate an overall negative perception of the availability of effective treatments.

The results indicate divided opinions regarding the availability of effective treatments for low back pain, with 43% of experts remaining neutral (neither agree nor disagree), 7% of participants strongly agreed with the availability of such treatments and 29% agreed. In addition to this, 14% of experts disagree and 7% strongly disagree, indicating a wide range of divergence of opinion on the current available effective treatments, with a neutral majority.

Similarly to low back pain, opinions are widely divided regarding the availability of effective treatments for falls. Almost half of the experts who selected falls (43%) remained neutral (neither agree nor disagree). 27% of participants agreed with the statement and 9% strongly

agreed. 18% of participants disagreed and strongly disagreed with the fact that there are effective treatments available for falls.

Experts were divided on the availability of effective treatments for headache disorders, with 27% agreeing and 27% disagreeing. 36% of participants remained neutral, and 9% strongly agree with the availability of effective treatments for headache disorders.

4.3.2.2. Treatment accessibility:

The following graphs summarize experts' opinions on the accessibility of current treatments for each disease:

Most experts (45%) considered the accessibility of treatments for depressive disorders to be sufficient (agree), and 27% remained neutral (neither agree nor disagree). On the other hand, 23% of participants who chose this disease considered treatments to not be accessible (disagree) and 5% strongly disagree.

81% of participants didn't consider that there are accessible treatments for AD and other dementias (56% disagree, 25% strongly disagree). However, 6% do agree that treatments are accessible for treating people with AD and other dementias, and 13% remained neutral (neither agree nor disagree).

The results show a mixed distribution of opinions among experts. For 29%, treatment accessibility was considered satisfactory, and 7% strongly agreed with the statement. On the other hand, 29% of participants disagree with the fact that treatments are accessible for treating people with low back pain and 7% strongly disagree. The remaining 29% neither agree nor disagree.

45% of experts agreed (of which 9% strongly agreed) with the statement expressing the treatment accessibility for falls. 36% remained neutral and 18% disagreed.

Regarding treatment accessibility for headache disorders, there is a lack of consensus, as 36% of experts disagreed, another 36% remained neutral and the final 27% agree that treatments are accessible for treating people with a headache.

4.3.2.3. Existence of prevention strategies:

The following graphs summarize experts' perceptions of the existence and effectiveness of prevention strategies for the diseases identified:

In terms of proven strategies to prevent depressive disorders, there is a clear lack of consensus as the results are widely distributed. 33% of experts agree (of which 5% strongly agree), however 46% disagree (of which 14% strongly disagree) with the statement that proven strategies to prevent depressive disorders exist. 23% of experts remained neutral.

Most experts (50%) considered that effective prevention strategies do not exist for AD and other dementias, along with 19% of experts who strongly disagreed, while 13% expressed moderate agreement with the statement (agree). A further 19% took a neutral stance (neither agree nor disagree). These results suggest a generally negative opinion regarding the existence of proven strategies to prevent AD and other dementias.

Regarding low back pain, the results show a mixed distribution of opinions among the experts. For 36% of participants, the existence of proven strategies to prevent low back pain was satisfactory (agree), and 7% strongly agreed. However, 36% expressed a disagreement with the statement, and 21% adopted a neutral position (neither agree nor disagree).

Most experts (45%) agree that there are proven strategies to prevent falls, and 18% strongly agree. 27% of experts remained neutral (neither agree nor disagree) and 9% disagree with the statement. These results indicate a lack of consensus, but with a higher number of experts who agree or strongly agree.

The results show a predominantly negative perception of prevention strategies for headache disorders with 64% of experts disagreeing with the statement (of which 9% strongly disagree). A smaller proportion of 9% agree and the remaining 27% neither agree nor disagree with the fact that there are proven strategies to prevent headache disorders.

4.3.2.4. Need for large medical cohorts:

The following graphs show experts' assessments of the need for large medical cohorts to fill data gaps:

Most of experts (82%) expressed the necessity of large medical cohorts to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of depressive disorders with 68% who agreed and 18% who strongly agreed. 14% of participants remained neutral (neither agree nor disagree), while no one expressed a negative opinion. These results indicate a clear consensus on the importance of LMedC to improve treatment and prevention strategies.

Regarding the need for LMedC to enhance and improve treatment and prevention of AD and other dementias, 31% of experts strongly agree and 56% agree, while 6% adopt a neutral position (neither agree nor disagree). 6% of experts have expressed a strong disagreement, but none expressed moderate disagreement with the statement.

These results indicate that 78% of experts strongly agree (21%) and agree (57%) that there is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance treatment and prevention of low back pain. 21% neither agreed nor disagreed.

Most experts support the need for LMedC studies to improve treatment and prevention strategies of fall. Indeed, 27% of experts strongly agreed and 45% agreed, while 18% neither agreed nor disagreed. On the other hand, 9% of participants expressed strong disagreement, but no experts expressed moderate disagreement.

All experts (100%) agreed on the importance of LMedC studies to enhance and improve treatment and prevention strategies for headache disorders. With 36% of experts who agreed and 64% strongly agreed. These results suggest a favourable consensus on the importance of large medical cohort studies for these strategies.

4.3.2.5. Need for population cohorts:

The results concerning the need for population cohorts to better understand the impact of diseases are presented in the following graphs:

Most experts agreed that depressive disorders require population cohorts (27% strongly agreed, 64% agreed), however 9% neither agreed nor disagreed.

All experts agreed on the need for population cohort studies to improve the treatment and prevention of Alzheimer’s disease and other dementias. 63% agreed and 37% strongly agreed.

Similarly to AD and other dementias, all participants agreed (71% agreed and 29% strongly agreed) on the need for population cohort studies to enhance and improve treatment and prevention of low back pain.

Concerning the use of population cohort studies to improve prevention and treatment of falls, 27% of participants strongly agreed, 64% agreed and 9% neither agreed nor disagreed.

All experts (100%) agree on the need for population cohort studies to enhance prevention and treatment of headache disorders, with 27% who strongly agreed and 73% who agreed.

4.3.2.6. Need for clinical cohorts:

The results concerning the need for clinical cohorts to better understand the impact of diseases are presented in the following graphs:

Most experts (73%) recognized the need for clinical cohort studies to improve prevention and treatment of depressive disorders (agree), and 9% strongly agreed. While 14% remain neutral (neither agree nor disagree), 5% expressed moderate disagreement.

Regarding AD and other dementias, 94% of experts recognized the necessity for clinical cohort studies to enhance prevention and treatment, with 31% of participants who strongly agreed and 63% who agreed. However, 6% expressed a strong negative opinion.

According to the table, 64% of experts agreed that low back pain indeed needs clinical cohort studies to enhance/improve prevention and treatment, along with 7% who strongly agreed. On the other hand, 7% expressed disagreement (disagree) and 21% expressed a neutral opinion (neither agree nor disagree).

The results suggest a majority of positive responses concerning the necessity for clinical cohort studies to enhance and improve prevention and treatment of falls. 18% of experts expressed strong agreement (strongly agree) and 45% expressed agreement (agree) with the statement. A smaller proportion 9% strongly disagreed while 27% of experts neither agreed nor disagreed.

Finally, most experts (90%) supported the need for clinical cohort studies to enhance and improve treatment and prevention of headache disorders and 10% adopted a neutral position (neither agree nor disagree).

4.4. Results Round 2

Following the results of the first round, the diseases most frequently mentioned by experts were selected. From this analysis, a list of 15 diseases was drawn up. The experts were then asked to select **three diseases from this list (Table 3)** and to answer a series of questions for each selected disease. This stage identified the final diseases on which a scoping review was performed.

Disease	Frequency
Mental disorders (depression, ADHD, anxiety...)	47
Rare diseases	29
Endometriosis	22
Alzheimer's disease and other dementias	19
Low back pain	16
Falls	13
Headache disorders	13
Age-related and other hearing loss	11
Pancreatic cancer	11
Stroke	9
Diabetes mellitus	6
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	6
Hypertensive heart disorder	4
Cystic fibrosis	3
Ischemic heart disease	1

Table 3 – Diseases selected by the experts from the 15-most frequently mentioned disease list in the previous phase.

The most selected diseases are **mental disorders (depression, ADHD, anxiety...), rare diseases, endometriosis, Alzheimer’s disease and other dementias and low back pain.**

The results obtained from the experts' Likert-scale assessments are used to analyse various aspects of unmet medical needs for each disease identified. Shown analyses cover dimensions of the **5 most selected** diseases such as the **availability and accessibility of effective treatments**, the existence of **prevention strategies**, and the need for **large medical (clinical) and population cohorts.**

4.4.1. General results

4.4.1.1. Treatment efficacy:

The following graphs present the experts' assessment of the perceived availability of effective treatments for the identified diseases:

The previous charts illustrate the experts' responses to the availability of effective treatments for mental disorders, rare diseases, endometriosis, AD and other dementias and low back pain.

Mental disorders (54% agree) and low back pain (44% agree) raise the most favourable perceptions of the availability of effective treatments. On the other hand, AD and other dementias (79% disagree and strongly disagree) and rare diseases (47% disagree and strongly disagree) generate a largely negative perception with much room for improvement. Finally, endometriosis (57% neither agree nor disagree) is distinguished by a majority of neutral respondents, reflecting a lack of information or opinion.

This analysis uncovers disparities in perceptions of effective treatment availability across the final conditions, highlighting areas where information campaigns or treatment improvements may be needed to address experts' doubts.

4.4.1.2. Treatment accessibility:

The following graphs summarize experts' opinions on the accessibility of current treatments for each disease:

Firstly, the results of treatment access for mental disorders, it seems acceptable by some (30%), but insufficient for a significant proportion of 37% of experts. Following the insufficiency, the areas rare diseases and AD and other dementias present the greatest dissatisfaction with access to treatments, with a majority of respondents disagreeing.

Regarding low back pain (44% agree), treatment access is perceived as relatively positive, despite disparities. Finally, endometriosis is the disease with the highest level of indecision, underlining the need to raise awareness or improve treatment accessibility.

These results highlight significant differences in perceived access to treatments, depending on the disease area, potentially requiring targeted actions to improve treatment access.

4.4.1.3.Existence of prevention strategies:

The following graphs summarize experts' perceptions of the existence and effectiveness of prevention strategies for the diseases identified

Based on the experts’ responses, the perception of preventive strategies is low/negative for most diseases, in particular rare diseases (60% disagree and strongly disagree), endometriosis (48% disagree and strongly disagree) and mental illnesses (45% disagree and strongly disagree). Alzheimer’s disease and other dementias is the disease area with the strongest disagreement regarding proven prevention strategies, with 79% of respondents disagreeing (53% disagree and 26% strongly disagree).

Low back pain (44% strongly agree and agree) is the only exception, with a more positive perception of preventive measures.

The lack of information, awareness and investment in prevention for certain pathologies appears to be a priority that needs to be addressed.

4.4.1.4. Need for large medical cohorts:

The following graphs show experts' assessments of the need for large medical cohorts to fill data gaps:

The need for large medical cohorts is almost unanimously recognized for all the disease areas selected by the experts. Levels of agreement vary slightly, but the conditions concerned by strong consensus are:

- Mental disorders (54% agree, 46% strongly agree) and low back pain (63% agree, 38% strongly agree) with 100% agreement.
- Alzheimer’s disease (37% agree, 58% strongly agree) and other dementias with 95% agreement, while 5% of experts remained neutral.

- Rare diseases (79% agree and strongly agree, 11% disagree, 11% remain neutral) and endometriosis (90% agree and strongly agree, 10% neither agree nor disagree) also benefit from general support, with a slight neutrality among a minority of respondents.

This consensus reflects a general recognition of the important role of large medical cohorts in improving research, treatment and prevention of these final conditions.

4.4.1.5. Need for population cohorts:

The results concerning the need for population cohorts to better understand the impact of diseases are presented in the following graphs:

The need for population cohort studies is largely acknowledged for most of the diseases considered, with particularly strong agreement for Alzheimer’s disease and other dementias (95% agree and strongly agree), low back pain (88% agree and strongly agree) and endometriosis (90% agree and strongly agree). Mental disorders’ (89% agree and strongly agree) responses also illustrate a high agreement with 11% of participants remaining neutral (neither agree nor disagree). On the other hand, rare diseases’ (68% agree and strongly agree) responses suggest more moderate support, with 14% expressing disagreement and 4% strong disagreement.

To conclude, population cohorts are seen as essential for research, prevention and treatment of these diseases. However, in the case of rare diseases, other types of cohort studies might need to be considered.

4.4.1.6. Need for clinical cohorts:

The results concerning the need for clinical cohorts to better understand the impact of diseases are presented in the following graphs:

Based on the results, overall, the need for clinical cohorts is very well recognized for all the disease areas evaluated, with a particularly strong agreement for AD and other dementias (53% agree and 47% strongly agree), as well as for endometriosis (62% agree and 33% strongly agree) and rare diseases (36% agree and 57% strongly agree).

Mental disorders (80% agree/strongly agree and 4% disagree) and low back pain (82% agree/strongly agree and 18% remain neutral) have a majority of experts' agreeing with the statement that there is a need for clinical cohorts to enhance/improve treatments of the latter conditions, although a notable degree of neutrality remains.

To conclude, clinical cohorts are seen as necessary for the enhancement and improvement of treatment and prevention of the final diseases selected by experts.

4.4.2. Diseases selected by experts for each field of work

The following graphs illustrate the results of the selected diseases within each expert field of work. Some experts selected more than one field of expertise due to their involvement in more than one area of work.

4.4.2.1. Clinical researchers

4.4.2.2. Epidemiology or public health researchers

4.4.2.3. Translational researchers

4.4.2.4. Cohort researchers

4.4.2.5. Civil and patient representatives

4.4.2.6. Physicians

4.4.2.7.Managers

4.5. Nominal Interviews

4.5.1. What are nominal interviews

Nominal interviews are a qualitative data collection technique distinguished by its simplicity and its focus on one individual at a time. As opposed to group methods such as focus groups, the nominal interview is a one-to-one interaction between the researcher and the participant (in this case, the expert). It is intended to collect detailed information about the individual's perceptions or opinions on a given topic.

This method enables exploration of the addressed subject, encouraging spontaneous expression on the part of participants, while minimizing the influence of group dynamics.

The purpose of nominal interviews is to understand complex phenomena, gather personal experiences, or explore sensitive subjects requiring a certain level of confidentiality and attention.

4.5.2. Objective

Following the results of the Delphi study performed, nominal interviews were carried out to reach a final consensus on the disease areas with unmet medical needs that could benefit from large medical cohorts. Additionally, another objective was to explore the challenges and limitations encountered by the experts when accessing and utilizing cohort data.

4.5.3. Recruitment Process

Figure 4 – Nominal Interviews Recruitment Process

4.5.4. Interview Process

The online nominal interviews began with a presentation of the results for the diseases most selected by the experts. These results included the frequency and percentage associated with each selected disease, providing an overview of the diseases considered as areas with unmet medical needs, potentially benefiting from large medical cohort studies.

Experts were then invited to share their opinion on these results, expressing whether the results aligned with their expectations or were surprising. This step enabled to gather initial qualitative feedback, highlight the participants’ reactions and perspectives.

Based on this input, experts were asked to narrow down their selection by choosing three diseases from the five most frequently cited. This prioritization step enabled the identification of the final diseases to be retained for further analysis.

Finally, the selected diseases were used as the basis for a literature review (scoping review). The aim of this review was to identify existing large medical cohorts (according to the project's established definition) evaluating these specific diseases, and to map these studies in the European landscape from 2019 to 2024.

4.5.5. Findings

4.5.5.1. Disease areas with unmet medical needs: final selection for mapping

As mentioned previously, the first step was to present to the participants the results of the Delphi study by displaying the chart of the most selected diseases (frequency and percentage of selection), which were mental disorders, rare diseases, endometriosis, AD and other dementias, and low back pain. Based on the discussions and consensus process, the final three diseases selected for the mapping phase are depression, AD and other dementias and endometriosis.

Mental disorders were mentioned by 18 experts during the nominal interviews, making them the most frequently mentioned disease area. They underlined their high prevalence and considerable impact on healthcare systems. Specific disorders such as depression and schizophrenia were identified as being particularly relevant, due to their high individual and public burden. Personality disorders were also mentioned as an urgent and poorly understood issue. This being said, the final decision was to conduct the mapping of large medical cohorts that evaluated all types of **depression** (depressive symptoms, major depressive disorder, seasonal affective disorders, etc.).

Regarding **Alzheimer's disease and other dementias**, this disease area was mentioned 15 times. Experts see it as a public health priority, given its high prevalence and burden. Moreover, they underlined the need for better understanding and further research to improve therapeutic interventions.

The final disease chosen for the mapping of large medical cohorts is **endometriosis**, mentioned 8 times. Experts highlighted the absence of evidence-based treatments and the inadequacy of available programs. Furthermore, endometriosis is seen as a major problem, due to its impact on patients' quality of life and the considerable need for a better understanding of its management and care.

Although rare diseases were mentioned 9 times and considered important by the experts, they were ultimately not selected for the mapping phase of the project. The main difficulty was to reach consensus on a specific sub-group of rare diseases on which to focus efforts. Muscular dystrophies, cystic fibrosis, rare neurological disorders and rare cancers were all proposed, but no clear agreement could be reached among the experts, making it then difficult to develop a coherent mapping strategy.

The final condition, low back pain was mentioned 6 times. It is perceived as one of the main causes of disability worldwide by certain experts. Although it has a significant impact, it was not selected for the mapping phase due to the higher priority given to the other conditions.

To conclude, expert reactions to the results varied considerably. Some were very satisfied, as the results closely matched their responses to the last round of the Delphi study. In contrast, others were very surprised, as they had expected various diseases to feature in the top five. Pathologies such as stroke, considered critical because of the serious consequences, cancer because of its lethality, and headaches because of their increasing prevalence worldwide, were among those that some experts thought would be prioritized.

5. MAPPING OF LARGE MEDICAL COHORTS

5.1. Scoping Review

To address the second objective of WP3: *identify areas of unmet medical need and opportunities for improved medical care*, a mapping analysis of large medical cohorts was proposed and conducted. The main aim of this analysis was to carry out a comprehensive search of existing resources within the LMedC cohort landscape in Europe.

The initial proposal was to conduct a systematic literature review, however, due to the broad nature and scope of the question, together with its explorative intention, a scoping review was finally conducted, which better fitted these characteristics. As such, scoping reviews are the preferred tool to map the existing evidence in a research area (Peters et al., 2015).

Following the results from the performed Delphi study, the scoping review was focused on the identified areas with unmet medical needs: depression, Alzheimer's disease and other dementias and endometriosis. The scoping review allowed to identify studies and publications analysing existing large European cohorts. Once these were identified, the studies based on the same LMedC were merged and the data extraction was performed to obtain information on each LMedC.

5.2. Objective

The objective of the current scoping review was to explore the existing cohort studies within the areas with unmet medical needs identified in the previous phase of the project: depression, Alzheimer's disease and other dementias and endometriosis in Europe. In that sense, the following scoping review was conducted: **European landscape of large medical cohorts: a scoping review.**

5.3. Methodology

5.3.1. Research design and review question

A scoping review was the selected methodology for the mapping of large medical cohorts, which followed the JBI methodology (Peters et al., 2020). The research question that the scoping review intended to answer was:

What are the existing large medical cohorts in Europe within the identified areas with unmet medical needs (endometriosis, Alzheimer's disease and other dementias and depression)?

The previously established definition for “large medical cohorts” was used for the scoping review.

5.3.2. Search strategy methods

The electronic database PUBMED was searched for publications from 2019 to 2024, limiting the search to the last 5 years. Three different searches were performed for the different identified areas. The search strategy was based on the following terms:

((depression[MeSH Terms]) AND (cohort study[MeSH Terms])) AND (europe[MeSH Terms])

((alzheimer's disease[MeSH Terms]) AND (cohort study[MeSH Terms])) AND (dementia[MeSH Terms]) AND (europe[MeSH Terms])

((endometriosis[MeSH Terms]) AND (cohort study[MeSH Terms])) AND (europe[MeSH Terms])

5.3.3. Eligibility criteria

The objective of the conducted scoping review was to map the existing efforts within the LMedC cohort landscape in Europe, meaning the core concept of the review are European LMedC. For that, the publications included in the scoping review had to study cohorts from European countries and that could be included in the previously established definition of LMedC:

A medical cohort refers to a group of individuals with a shared condition, characteristic or exposure who might be followed over time to collect extensive health-related data and/or biological materials for current and future health research. The data and biological materials collected from a medical cohort are stored as databank and/or biobank collections. In this project, we neither consider interventional clinical trials nor databanks based on health registries without specific follow-up as medical cohorts. We consider a medical cohort as “large”:

- *A clinical cohort (observational) comprising over 1000 participants selected for a health condition; or*
- *A rare disease cohort comprising over 0,5-1% (as a rough guideline) of the total disease population of the country; or*
- *A population cohort comprising over 10000 participants.*

The scoping review also focused on the identified areas in the previous phase of the project: endometriosis, Alzheimer’s disease and other dementias and depression.

In order to systematically assess whether the screened publications met the previous criteria, a series of inclusion and exclusion criteria were defined according to the PCC (Population, Concept, and Context), in line with the recommendations of the JBI (Peters et al., 2020) (**Table 4**).

	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
--	---------------------------	---------------------------

<p>Population</p>	<p>Clinical diagnosis of [Depression / Alzheimer’s disease and other dementias / Endometriosis]</p> <p>General population with [Depression / Alzheimer’s disease and other dementias / Endometriosis] as an outcome</p>	<p>Initial population with a different condition</p> <p>Studies focusing on other diseases/characteristics</p>
<p>Concept: Cohort</p> <p>• Cohort size:</p>	<p>Group of individuals with a shared condition, characteristic or exposure who might be followed over time to collect extensive health-related data and/or biological materials for current and future health research</p> <p>- Clinical cohorts comprising at least 1000 participants;</p> <p>- Population cohorts comprising at least 10000 participants</p>	<p>Studies with smaller cohort sizes</p>
<p>Context:</p> <p>• Geographical location</p>	<p>European countries</p>	<p>Countries outside of Europe</p>

Types of evidence sources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study design 	Cohort studies	Interventional clinical trials, biobank/register-based studies without follow-up, medical records-based studies
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data collection 	Cohort study with Interview / questionnaires without health examination; Cohort study with Interview / questionnaires with health examination; Cohort study with Interview / questionnaires with biological samples
	Studies with follow-up	Studies without follow-up
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Follow-up • Publication year 	2019-2024	Other publication year

Table 4 – Inclusion and exclusion criteria for the present scoping review defined according to the PCC.

Included studies had to include participants with a diagnosis of the selected diseases or disorders (clinical cohort) or to study these as an outcome (population cohort). Studies focused on a clinical cohort with a different diagnosis were excluded from the review.

Included cohorts had to collect data from participants over time (follow-up) through interviews or questionnaires with or without health examinations and/or biological samples, with a research purpose. Studies without follow-up, interventional clinical trials, biobank/register-based studies without a specific follow-up with research purposes and medical records-based studies were excluded from the review.

The search was limited to the last 5 years, in order to limit the results obtained and collect information on the most recent cohort studies. Only publications in English were included.

5.3.4. Manuscript selection

5.3.4.1. Abstract review

Retrieved abstracts from the PUBMED search were screened against the pre-defined eligibility criteria (described above). Abstracts excluded by the reviewers at this abstract review stage were disregarded. Discrepancies about inclusion were resolved by consensus between the reviewers, or by a third party when consensus could not be reached. Publications meeting the eligibility criteria were downloaded and registered in a spreadsheet file.

5.3.4.2. Full-text review

The screening process was repeated for those publications selected for inclusion after abstract review, using the full text articles. A record was kept of publications excluded at this stage along with the rationale for their exclusion (see **Appendix C**). PMIDs, author(s), year of publication, article name, cohort name, sample size, cohort type, country, link to PUBMED, final decision and reason for exclusion were tracked at this stage. The approach for resolving uncertainty regarding inclusion of publications was the same as for abstract review. All publications included after completion of the full-text review were retained for data extraction.

The process was repeated independently for each search. A PRISMA flow chart for each study selection procedure has been prepared.

5.3.5. Data extraction and cohort identification

Before data extraction began, a standardised data extraction form and data extraction guidelines were defined. An independent extraction sheet was used for the three different searches (depression, Alzheimer’s disease and other dementias and endometriosis). Extracted variables, their possible values (if applicable) and instructions for extraction of each variable are indicated in **Table 5**.

Variable	Possible values (if applicable)	Instructions
Name of cohort study		Name of the cohort study as it appears in the publication.
Type of cohort	Clinical cohort Population cohort	Clinical cohorts focus on patients with specific conditions, while population cohorts represent a larger, broader sample.
DOI (Digital Object Identifier)		DOI for the publication associated with the cohort study.
Title of manuscript		Full title of the paper or article that reports on the cohort study.
Author(s)		
Year of publication	2019, 2020, 2021, 2023, 2024	

<p>Study design</p>	<p>General prospective cohort study</p> <p>Nested case-control study</p> <p>Case-cohort study</p> <p>Multi-center cohort study</p> <p>Exposure-specific cohort study</p> <p>Birth or age-based cohort study</p> <p>Retrospectively constructed prospective cohort study</p> <p>Disease-oriented cohort study</p> <p>Other (Specify)</p>	
<p>Country</p>	<p>Albania, Andorra, Armenia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Kosovo, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Moldova, Monaco, Montenegro, Netherlands,</p>	<p>“Europe” had to be input when the cohort spanned multiple countries.</p>

	<p>North Macedonia, Norway, Poland, Portugal</p> <p>Romania, San Marino, Serbia, Slovakia</p> <p>Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland</p> <p>Ukraine, United Kingdom, Vatican City</p> <p>Europe</p>	
<p>Disease/disorder</p>	<p>A/ Major depressive disorder Depressive symptoms Seasonal affective disorder Postpartum depression Atypical depression Premenstrual dysphoric disorder Persistent depressive disorder Psychotic depression Depression due to substance use</p>	<p>Different possible values depending on each search for each disease/disorder:</p> <p>A/ Depression</p> <p>B/ Alzheimer’s disease and other dementias</p> <p>C/ Endometriosis</p>

	<p>Other</p> <p>B/</p> <p>Alzheimer's disease</p> <p>Parkinson's disease</p> <p>Lewy body</p> <p>Vascular dementia</p> <p>Mixed dementia</p> <p>Frontotemporal dementia</p> <p>Other dementia</p> <p>C/</p> <p>NA</p>	
Sample size		Total number of participants whose data were
Type of population	<p>General population (country representative)</p> <p>General population (geographic region)</p> <p>General population (age-specific group(s))</p>	

	<p>General population (gender-specific group(s))</p> <p>Occupational groups</p> <p>Ethnic/racial groups</p> <p>Socioeconomic groups</p> <p>Rural population</p> <p>Urban population</p> <p>Patients with specific disease</p> <p>Patients undergoing a specific treatment</p> <p>High-risk individuals</p> <p>Patients with specific symptoms</p> <p>Disease registries</p> <p>Health system/insurance enrollees</p> <p>Other (Specify)</p>	
<p>Age range of population</p>	<p><18 years</p> <p>≥18 years</p> <p>All ages</p>	

<p>Frequency of follow-up</p>	<p>Monthly</p> <p>1-6 months</p> <p>7-12 months</p> <p>More than 1 year and less than 5 years</p> <p>More than 5 years and less than 10 years</p> <p>10 years or more</p> <p>Irregular/as needed</p>	
<p>Number of follow-ups</p>	<p>Single follow-up</p> <p>Multiple follow-ups</p> <p>Continuous follow-ups</p> <p>Cross-sectional</p>	
<p>Total duration of follow-up</p>		<p>Total duration of time over which participants were followed, from the start of the study to the last follow-up</p>
<p>Type of information collected</p>	<p>Interview/questionnaires without health examination</p> <p>Interview/questionnaires with health examination</p>	

	Interview/questionnaires with biological samples	
--	--	--

Table 5 – Variables, possible values and instructions for data extraction.

Relevant information was extracted from the selected publications and collected in a spreadsheet. Once the data extraction was finalized, publications studying the same cohort were put together and the extracted data was combined to summarize the information on each LMedC.

Results have been reported following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) guidelines Tricco et al., 2018).

5.4. Final Mapping Results

5.4.1. Depression results

The initial search in PUBMED allowed the identification of 1431 records. After title and abstract review, 1210 publications were excluded, leaving 252 for full-text review. From those, 94 were excluded during that step. The screening process is shown in **Figure 5**. Main reasons for exclusion were: biobank or registry-based cohort studies without specific follow-up as a medical cohort, studies with population cohorts with less than 10000 participants or clinical cohorts with less than 1000, medical-chart based studies, studies without follow-up data and cohorts with or studies focusing on outcomes different than depression. In total, 158 publications were retrieved for data extraction. All extracted information from included publications can be found in **Appendix D, Tables 10 and 11**.

Figure 5 – PRISMA flowchart for depression studies. From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71.

After data extraction and combination, 48 different cohorts were identified (**Table 6**). Of them, 46 were population cohorts and 2 clinical. The clinical cohorts included participants with depression and/or anxiety. The majority of the population cohorts were of country-representative general population (17) or general population of specific geographic regions (7), but also of age-specific groups (13). The rest of cohorts comprised more specific

populations: occupational groups (3), twin population (2), women giving birth (2), university graduates (1) and ethnic groups (1).

The majority of cohorts were from a specific country (45), specifically, identified cohorts were from the following countries: the United Kingdom (17), Denmark (6), Sweden (4), the Netherlands (4), Finland (3), France (3), Germany (3), Norway (2), Iceland (1), Poland (1) and Spain (1). Three cohorts included participants from different countries.

In terms of sample size, 17 population cohorts presented between 10000 and 19999 participants, 19 between 20000 and 99999 and 10 cohorts 100000 participants or more. Clinical cohorts presented sample sizes of 27776 and 1701 participants, respectively.

Name of Cohort Study	Type of cohort	Type of population	Country	Sample size
1958 British birth cohort (National Child Development Study (NCDS))	Population	general population (age-specific group(s))	United Kingdom	17415
1970 British Cohort Study	Population	general population (age-specific group(s))	United Kingdom	17000
Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children (ALSPAC)	Population	general population (geographic region)	United Kingdom	14500
Bochum Optimism and Mental Health (BOOM) Study	Population	general population (age-specific group(s))	Europe	40000
Born in Bradford	Population	general population (geographic region)	United Kingdom	60000
Child and Adolescent Twin Study in Sweden (CATSS)	Population	twin population	Sweden	17220
Cognitive Function and Ageing Studies (CFAS I & II)	Population	general population (age-specific group(s))	United Kingdom	15000
Constances cohort	Population	general population (country representative)	France	200000
COVID-19 Psychiatry and Neurological Genetics study (COPING)	Clinical	anxiety or depression	United Kingdom	27776

Danish Blood Donor Study (DBDS)	Population	general population (country representative)	Denmark	150000
Danish Longitudinal Study of Ageing (DLSA)	Population	general population (country representative)	Denmark	13500
Danish National Birth Cohort (DNBC)	Population	general population (country representative)	Denmark	100000
Danish Work Environment Cohort Study (DWECS)	Population	occupational groups	Denmark	11967
English Longitudinal Study of Ageing (ELSA)	Population	general population (country representative)	United Kingdom	19000
EPIC-Norfolk Study	Population	general population (age-specific group(s))	United Kingdom	30000
Etude Longitudinale Française depuis l'Enfance (ELFE)	Population	general population (age-specific group(s))	France	18000
Generation Scotland	Population	general population (geographic region)	United Kingdom	40000
German National Cohort (NAKO)	Population	general population (country representative)	Germany	205000
Gutenberg Health Study (GHS)	Population	general population (country representative)	Germany	18500
Health and Social Support Study (HeSSup) cohort	Population	general population (country representative)	Finland	24057

Health, Alcohol, and Psychosocial factors In Eastern Europe (HAPIEE) study	Population	general population (age-specific group(s))	Europe	36500
Helsinki Birth Cohort Study	Population	general population (geographic region)	Finland	13345
Integrative Psychiatric Research (iPSYCH) Consortium	Population	general population (country representative)	Denmark	130000
Lifelines Cohort Study	Population	general population (country representative)	Netherlands	167729
Millennium Cohort Study (MCS)	Population	general population (country representative)	United Kingdom	13135
Million Women Study	Population	general population (age-specific group(s))	United Kingdom	1300000
Netherlands Study of Depression and Anxiety (NESDA)	Clinical	anxiety and/or depression	Netherlands	1701
Next steps	Population	general population (age-specific group(s))	United Kingdom	19000
Next Stop: Mum of the postpartum depression prevention (PPD) strategy in Poland	Population	women giving birth	Poland	21500
Northern Finland 1966 Birth Cohort	Population	general population (geographic region)	Finland	20000
Norwegian Mother and Child Cohort (MoBa)	Population	women giving birth	Norway	90000
Norwegian Nord-Trøndelag Health Study (HUNT)	Population	general population (geographic region)	Norway	230000

NutriNet-Santé cohort study	Population	general population (country representative)	France	26730
PART Study (Psykisk hälsa, Arbete och Relationer: Mental Health, Work, and Relationships).	Population	general population (geographic region)	Sweden	10074
Platform for Research Online to investigate Genetics and Cognition in Ageing Study (PROTECT)	Population	general population (age-specific group(s))	United Kingdom	25000
Seguimiento Universidad de Navarra (SUN)	Population	university graduates	Spain	22500
Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE)	Population	general population (country representative)	Europe	160000
Swedish Longitudinal Occupational Survey of Health (SLOSH)	Population	occupational groups	Sweden	18915
Swedish National March Cohort study (SNMC)	Population	general population (country representative)	Sweden	43863
The COVID-19 Social Study	Population	general population (country representative)	United Kingdom	70000
The German Ageing Survey (DEAS)	Population	general population (age-specific group(s))	Germany	20715
The Healthy Life in an Urban Setting (HELIUS) study	Population	ethnic/racial groups	Netherlands	14789
The Older Persons and Informal Caregivers Survey Minimal Data Set (TOPICS-MDS)	Population	general population (age-specific group(s))	Netherlands	46456

Twins UK	Population	twin population	United Kingdom	15000
UK Biobank	Population	general population (country representative)	United Kingdom	500000
United Kingdom Household Longitudinal Study	Population	general population (country representative)	United Kingdom	40000
Work Environment and Health in Denmark (WEHD)	Population	occupational groups	Denmark	34960
Youth in Iceland Study	Population	general population (age-specific group(s))	Iceland	59701

Table 6 – Identified European cohorts for depression studies.

5.4.2. AD and other dementias results

The initial search in PUBMED allowed the identification of 243 records. After title and abstract review, 159 publications were excluded, leaving 84 for full-text review. From those, 41 were excluded during that step. The screening process is shown in **Figure 6**. Main reasons for exclusion were: studies with population cohorts with less than 10000 participants or clinical cohorts with less than 1000, biobank or registry-based cohort studies without specific follow-up as a medical cohort, medical-chart based studies, studies focusing on outcomes different than AD and other dementias and studies without follow-up data. In total, 43 publications were retrieved for data extraction. All extracted information from included publications can be found in **Appendix D, Tables 12 and 13**.

Figure 6 – PRISMA flowchart for AD and other dementias studies. From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71.

After data extraction and combination, 16 different cohorts were identified (**Table 7**). Half of them (8) were population cohorts and the other half clinical cohorts (8). Four clinical cohorts included a mixture of participants with different diagnosis or conditions, including mild cognitive symptoms (SCD, MCI), and/or AD and other dementia diagnosis (PD, FTD, DLB, VaD, and other less prevalent dementias). The other four clinical cohorts included only participants with AD diagnosis (2) and with mild cognitive symptoms (2). Regarding population cohorts, 3 were of country-representative general population, 2 of age-specific groups, and one of each of the following: general population of specific geographic regions, occupational groups and twin population.

In terms of geographic distribution, almost all identified cohorts were from a specific country (15). Specifically, identified cohorts were from the following countries: Sweden (5), the United Kingdom (3), Denmark (3), France (2), the Netherlands (1) and Spain (1). One cohort (GERAS) included participants from different countries.

The distribution of sample sizes for identified population cohorts is as follows: 4 between 10000 and 19999 participants, 3 between 20000 and 99999 and 1 cohort with 100000 participants or more. The majority of clinical cohorts (5)

presented between 1000 and 1999, 2 between 2000 and 9999, and 1 cohort with 10000 participants or more.

Name of Cohort Study	Type of cohort	Type of population	Country	Sample size
Amsterdam Dementia Cohort (ADC)	Clinical	SCD, MCI, AD, FTD, DLB	Netherlands	7000
Copenhagen City Heart Study (CCHS)	Population	general population (country representative)	Denmark	10369
Copenhagen General Population Study (CGPS)	Population	general population (country representative)	Denmark	17000
Danish Nurses Cohort (DNC)	Population	occupational groups	Denmark	25651
English Longitudinal Study of Ageing (ELSA)	Population	general population (age-specific group(s))	United Kingdom	19000
European Prospective Investigation into Cancer and Nutrition (EPIC)-Spain Dementia Cohort Study	Population	general population (geographic region)	Spain	25015
GERAS	Clinical	AD	Europe	1497
Impact of Cholinergic Treatment Use (ICTUS) study	Clinical	AD	France	1375
MEMENTO cohort	Clinical	very mild to mild cognitive impairment or isolated cognitive complaints	France	2323
Swedish BioFINDER study I	Clinical	SCD, MCI, AD, VaD, DLB, FTD, PD, other dementias	Sweden	1200
Swedish BioFINDER study II	Clinical	SCD, MCI, AD, VaD, DLB, FTD, PD, other dementias	Sweden	1910
Swedish BioFINDER study Memory clinic	Clinical	cognitive symptoms	Sweden	1200

Swedish Dementia Registry (SveDem)	Clinical	AD, VaD, mixed dementia, DLB, FTD, PD, unspecified dementia, other dementia types	Sweden	121218
Swedish Twin Registry	Population	twin population	Sweden	87000
UK Biobank	Population	general population (country representative)	United Kingdom	500000
Whitehall II study	Population	general population (age-specific group(s))	United Kingdom	10308

Table 7 – Identified European cohorts for AD and other dementias studies.

Figure 7 – PRISMA flowchart for endometriosis. From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71.

The publication allowed the identification of a clinical cohort, the Visanne Post-approval Observational Study (VIPOS) (**Table 8**). This was a prospective, observational, long-term cohort study, which followed women under hormonal treatment for endometriosis. It was conducted in six different European countries and collected self-reported questionnaires and clinically-verified data on almost 30000 women. The cohort was follow-up continuously, with contacts every 12 months after the initial contacts, up to 7 years.

Name of Cohort Study	Type of cohort	Type of population	Country	Sample size
Visanne Post-approval Observational Study (VIPOS)	Clinical	general population (gender-specific group(s))	Europe	27840

Table 8 – Identified European cohorts for endometriosis studies.

6. GUIDANCE ON NEEDS OF LMedC TO BE SUPPORTED BY A RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

6.1. Objective

An analysis of current needs of LMedC was performed to address the objective 3 of the WP3: To guide more effective decision-making and research efforts and support the development of a next-generation research infrastructure (RI) to streamline the use of cohort data and samples, now and in the future.

This analysis was focused on the key areas and cohorts previously identified and intended to extract existing gaps and barriers for the standardised use, management and sustainment of LMedC.

6.2. Delphi Study

During the Delphi study, some questions were added in relation to the status of the current European cohorts:

“What do you think should be done on a European level to improve the availability of cohorts to address unmet medical needs?”

“Do you have feedback, opinions, or suggestions regarding the use of large medical cohorts in improving medical care for the diseases you mentioned earlier? Please feel free to share any insights or recommendations you believe could enhance research and patient outcomes in the selected fields.”

6.3. Nominal Interviews

During the nominal interviews, experts were consulted on the *current limitations or challenges in accessing and utilizing cohort data that should be addressed by a next-generation research infrastructure*. Responses were gathered and common ideas were categorized and summarized.

6.4. Key challenges and needs

4 relevant topics were identified from the insights shared by the experts:

1. Data scope and representativity
2. Data quality and structure
3. Data access and sharing
4. Methodological and operational challenges

The specific ideas mentioned by the experts in each of the topics are explained below:

6.4.1. Data scope and representativity

While the number of existing European cohort studies can be high, many of these studies present important limitations in their data. Some of the main observed deficiencies are:

- Insufficient follow-up. Many cohort studies can be found that have collected data only in a few follow-ups, in some cases even only during the initial assessments. In these cohorts, longitudinal analysis cannot be performed, precluding the monitoring of the outcomes of interest over time or the description of the progression of the disease or condition.
- Disparity across medical areas. There is a clear imbalance of the number of existing cohorts depending on the related disorder. Some diseases, such as the ones with the most studied genetic factors or the most prevalent, attract most of the attention and their number of existing cohort studies is larger. This is why it is important to identify areas of unmet medical needs in terms of availability of medical cohorts. Moreover, the most prevalent diseases can also be more easily studied in general population cohorts, while less prevalent diseases often remain excluded.
 - Population bias.
- General population cohorts tend to include a specific profile of individuals, with a higher education level, a specific socioeconomic situation and increased health and wellbeing.

- The characteristics of some population groups (such as non-literate or socially disadvantaged individuals) often difficult their access to research initiatives, despite possible actions in study designs to arrive to the whole population. This results in the frequent exclusion of vulnerable groups in the generated cohorts.

These cohorts are therefore less representative of the population, generating a significant potential bias in the research results. In this sense, when analysing them caution needs to be taken when extracting conclusions, which may not be extendable to the whole population.

6.4.2. Data quality and structure

- Lack of standardization. Existing cohorts or datasets were created with different objectives, purposes and/or research questions and were therefore designed to approach them. As a result, these cohorts and datasets greatly differ from each other both in general issues such as data collection and variables, structure or type of follow-up, to specific ones, such as clinical criteria or measurement instruments. This lack of uniformity hinders collective research efforts to manage and work on them.
- Incomplete data. Clinical data is commonly presented with a high proportion of missing values, limiting its quality. Moreover, it may be found in varying formats due to differences in digitalization.
- The creation of a cohort may also generate a population bias, as previously discussed, which finally affects the representativeness of the data and the quality of the derived conclusions.

6.4.3. Data access and sharing

- Data protection legislation. Since 2018, the EU has adopted the GDPR legislation. This regulation represented an important effort to increase protection of the privacy rights of subjects. However, this regulation has created new barriers for data sharing with non-EU states, with different privacy restrictions and legislations, but also inside the EU, due to

lack of uniformity of application across EU member states. This limits the creation of cross-country cohorts, as well as the use of data from different countries.

- Data sharing regulations. In addition to the GDPR, some countries or even regions present more restrictive laws, which further difficult both data sharing and harmonization. This is the case, for example, of Ireland, with the Data Protection Acts.
- Data sharing reluctance. While there is increasing interest in research towards data sharing, transparency and openness (Waithira et al., 2019), researchers can be reluctant to share their collected data, mainly for reasons of intellectual property protection or concern of research competition.

6.4.4. Methodological and operational challenges

- Technical barriers in data analysis. The optimal analysis of some complex data types (such as the integration of genomics, imaging and clinical data), may require advanced methodologies and techniques that imply a certain level of expertise and specialization. Moreover, the lack of interoperable systems also represents a limitation.
- Lack of interconnected registries and initiatives. Many European countries have established registries of health and research data, which are available for research use. However, existing registries are not interconnected, they even may be structured differently. The same applies for current cohort studies, which are far from being harmonised or interconnected. This hinders cross-country research and limits analysis of data from different sources.
- Resource-intensive setup and maintenance. As any other study, cohort studies require an initial investment, for its design and start-up. But more importantly, due to their longitudinal nature, there is a need for continuous provision of funding and resources for their follow-up and maintenance. This represents an important obstacle for research institutions, as grants do not normally allow for a persistent provision of funding. Funding discontinuation may eventually lead to the abandonment of some studies, or to their loss of quality. In addition, funding is mostly prioritized for data valorisation, discriminating primary data collection.

6.5. Recommendations

Having identified the most challenging barriers for LMedC, consulted experts also offered possible solutions and recommendations, some directed to manage specific limitations, and others that could be applied on a higher level.

In that sense, experts agreed that the generation of an overarching common European infrastructure could and should give answer to all the current challenges. Moreover, it would set the framework for future cohort generation and would link existing ones. The proposed infrastructure should address the identified challenges as follows:

6.5.1. Data scope and representativity & Data quality and structure:

Harmonization: The infrastructure would need to set a standard of harmonization of newly collected data, as well as provide guidelines and best practices for standardized protocols to ensure the harmonization, linking and comparability of currently existing cohorts. This would generate uniformity between cohorts, allowing replicability and combined analysis. New cohorts would also follow these standardized protocols and present a shared structure and defined follow-up methodology, reducing disparities, missingness and possible biases.

Development of European population cohorts: the establishment of large-scale, population-wide cohorts across Europe, with comprehensive and representative data of quality represents an outstanding opportunity and would have a significant impact on research.

6.5.2. Data access and sharing:

GDPR and data regulation compliance: the infrastructure could establish a defined common path for data regulation compliance, facilitating and expediting data sharing between institutional partners.

Open datasets promotion: a general framework for open-access datasets could be defined to help ensuring proper data sharing and use, encouraging researchers and institutions and reducing mistrust. This would greatly benefit research advances, not only in Europe, but worldwide, as well as international collaborations.

Use of federated analysis: aligning on and encouraging federated analysis, even the generation of federated architectures or federated data platforms would improve data access, solving data privacy concerns.

6.5.3. Methodological and operational challenges:

Methodological standardization: Generation of methodological guidelines, even for complex analysis, that would ensure the comparability of the different analysis and results, reduce technical heterogeneity and variability. This would also facilitate the training of new professionals, as well as results discussions between experts. This in combination with the previously mentioned harmonization would simplify working with different cohorts.

6.5.4. Transversal matters:

A common infrastructure could also address other relevant transversal topics including:

Interdisciplinary communication: the infrastructure would need to include experts on different areas and a broad range of stakeholders, including researchers, clinicians, institutions, policymakers and user communities, among others. Interaction between these groups is fundamental for cohort studies, especially for complex diseases.

Collaborative networks: the infrastructure would also provide a great environment to promote collaboration between different teams and institutions, facilitating multicentric studies. This could also encourage data and resource sharing and allow a space of discussion to align on a common strategy.

Funding and policy support: a support structure or department could also be generated, focused on providing funding and policy support to help maintaining sustainable cohort studies, as well as the creation of new cohorts for identified gaps. New opportunities could also be identified and channelled through the common infrastructure.

FAIR principles

An additional final comment needs to be made relating to the FAIR principles. All work done within the infrastructure needs to clearly reflect the “FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship” (Wilkinson et al., 2016). These principles are directed to improve data usability and include the following elements: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. Importantly, FAIR principles apply not only to the data itself, but also to the metadata (information describing the data).

The previous recommendations for the research infrastructure have already reflected the importance of data Access, Interoperability and Reusability, but a special mention is also needed for the Findable element. Hence, data in cohort studies should be available and identifiable in a database record, and have complete, extense and well-organized metadata, describing the data and providing instructions for their use.

7. DISCUSSION

7.1. Key findings

LMedC DEFINITION

In order to frame the scope of the current project, the first goal of the current work was to define the concept of Large Medical Cohort. This concept resulted from the sum of three different parts, which had to be deeply assessed, both individually and as a whole: the concept of cohort, the medical context and the dimension. The final definition, while complex, greatly reflects what it can be generally understood as a large medical cohort for scientific purposes, highlighting the importance of the research-oriented goal and of its longitudinal nature. Nevertheless, it has to be mentioned that it is a working definition, and it is subject to further modifications.

GAP ANALYSIS: IDENTIFIED DISEASES

The question of which diseases are under-researched, thus contributing to unmet medical needs in Europe, is key to identifying areas requiring greater attention and investment. A Delphi study with two rounds was conducted to solve this question. In the first round, in the open question experts spontaneously identified mental disorders, AD/Dementia, endometriosis, rare diseases and pancreatic cancer as areas of interest for this field. Then, from the list of diseases with greatest impact in terms of disease burden (DALYs), the main selected diseases were depressive disorders, AD and other dementias, low back pain, falls and headache disorders. Interestingly, depression and AD and other dementias were mentioned in both lists, meaning that much research and organization efforts are still needed even in diseases with great burden.

Finally, during the second round of the Delphi study, four key disease categories emerged as particularly underserved due to insufficient research: mental disorders, rare diseases, endometriosis, and AD and other dementias.

Mental disorders, including depression, anxiety disorders, ADHD and schizophrenia was, by far, the main identified area with significant research gaps. Despite the growing burden of mental health problems in Europe, much research remains underfunded, and treatment options are often insufficient or outdated. This gap deprives many patients of the comprehensive care and support they need, contributing to the public health challenges surrounding mental health.

Rare diseases, such as cystic fibrosis, often face challenges due to their low prevalence (162,428 worldwide, Guo et Al. 2022), making it difficult to conduct large-scale clinical trials or obtain research funding. As a result, patients with these diseases often have limited access to effective treatments and diagnostic tools, creating a significant gap in healthcare.

According to the World Health Organization (2021), endometriosis is a condition that affects around 10% (190 million) number of women and girls of reproductive age. This condition also suffers from a lack of research, leading to societal and healthcare system challenges that contribute to delayed diagnosis and inadequate care.

Neurological disorders, notably Alzheimer's disease (AD), Parkinson's disease and other dementias, also present significant research gaps. These disorders have complex, multifactorial causes, therefore making it challenging to study and understand their underlying mechanisms. Although these disorders affect millions of people, e.g. AD affects 5,05% of the European population (Niu et Al. 2016), the pace of the development of new treatments remains slow, leaving patients and caregivers with limited options to manage symptoms and improve quality of life.

Notably, when the results of the Delphi study were presented to the experts during nominal interviews, many experts showed agreement with the results, even though others considered some other diseases, such as stroke, cancer or headache, should have been

included. While these mentioned diseases have a great impact on society and are among the most prevalent ones, our results show experts have mainly highlighted diseases with either a lack of research, such as endometriosis or rare diseases, or with insufficient treatments and delays in diagnosis, which is the case for both mental disorders and AD and other dementias.

Considering these previous results, nominal interviews allowed to reach a consensus, and the final three selected areas for the mapping phase were depression, endometriosis and AD and other dementias. Mental disorders, with a special focus on depression and AD and other dementias were the main disorders mentioned during this phase, because of their prevalence and their previously mentioned burden. The following mentioned type were rare diseases, however, as a broad group of diseases, the scoping review could not be performed on all of them, and consensus between experts on which to focus could not be reached.

MAPPING OF LMedC

The conducted scoping review allowed to identify a total of 65 cohorts from the three areas of interest (48 for depression, 16 for AD and other dementias and 1 for endometriosis), from the 202 selected publications. In general, this number seems low, especially from the large number of screened publications, but it is in line with the results from the gap analysis, as these disorders were selected due to their lack of data from cohort studies. In fact, for example in the first round of the Delphi study there was total consensus among consulted experts on the need for large medical cohorts to support treatment and prevention for both AD and other dementias and endometriosis (strong or moderate agreement), and for most experts in the case of mental disorders. The low number of identified cohorts reinforces this need.

In the case of depression, the number of identified records after the initial search was high (1431), meaning research using longitudinal studies is frequent for this disease. Depression or depressive symptoms, together with anxiety, were analyzed in many epidemiological

studies. Despite that, in recent years there has been an increase of research using health-related registries, without specific research goals and follow-up, and finally, the proportion of included publications was much lower. It is also worth noting that of the 48 identified LMedC cohorts, only 2 were clinical, meaning depression cohorts have not been established, but studies use population cohorts, mainly of general population.

In the case of AD and other dementias, even though less LMedC cohorts were identified, the proportion of clinical and population cohorts was half for each. The establishment of these clinical cohorts, which help to understand the course and progression of the disease, as well as their mechanisms, indicates there has been an increase in research, and even resources (Pavlik et al., 2022).

Regarding endometriosis, only 1 cohort could be identified. This is in line with results from the Delphi study, in which consensus was reached for the statement: *endometriosis requires clinical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention*. Experts also highlighted the need for a better understanding of its management and care, and the absence of therapeutic options. Therefore, both our results from the gap analysis and from the mapping of LMedC indicate that more research efforts should focus on endometriosis. Many of the screened publications used nationwide registries, which can provide real world data on diagnosis, used treatments, and even information on common comorbidities. However, research in endometriosis could greatly benefit from the establishment of specific longitudinal cohorts designed to study endometriosis, which would allow to understand the basis of the disease, its pathology and molecular pathways.

The country with more cohorts was the United Kingdom, with 20/61 cohorts (from the cohorts with participants from only one country). It is also worth noting that the number of cohorts comprising more than one country was surprisingly low: only 4 out of the 65 identified cohorts. This is also in agreement with what was commented by experts, when they were asked about recommendations and future directions of the field. Among the possible reasons for that there is the lack of standardization and agreement between countries and

research institutions. In that sense, efforts are still needed to generate comprehensive cohorts across Europe. These cohorts would represent an invaluable resource for research.

A final comment for the mapping process relates to the sample size of the LMedC definition. In the previous phases of the WP3, it was established that a “large” cohort would refer to these cohorts with more than 10000 and 1000 participants (for population and clinical cohorts, respectively). After the initial search for the scoping review, 1431, 243 and 105 publications were identified, for each of the selected disorders. An important proportion of these had to be excluded during the screening phase of the review as the sample size of the population did not meet our LMedC sample size criteria, which was the most repeated reason for exclusion during abstract review. Even though the criteria was defined based on the opinion of consortium members, if this had been reduced to 5000 and 500, or even 2500 and 250, the number of identified cohorts would have been higher. Nevertheless, some of the identified cohorts presented really large sample sizes, with 33/54 population cohorts with more than 20000 participants, and 5/11 clinical cohorts with more than 2000 participants.

GUIDANCE ON LMedC NEEDS

In order to address the last objective of the WP3, which intended to guide decision-making and efforts for the future RI, we took advantage of the opportunity provided by the Delphi study and the nominal interviews to consult experts. We included questions that allowed us to identify existing barriers and obtain recommendations to approach them. Answers from this section confirmed that the development of a next-generation research infrastructure could solve many of the identified issues relating to medical cohorts, paving the way for future research. Some of the mainly commented problems, which could be effectively solved, relate to data quality, lack of comparability and obstacles for data sharing. A RI could provide a framework for cohort creation and harmonization, and set the standards for the data use and access.

7.2. Strengths and Limitations

An important limitation of the current work relates to the established definition of LMedC. While a methodological approach was followed, some of the concepts that it entails are subject to interpretation, meaning other researchers would have selected slightly different perimeters. Moreover, it is possible that this definition does not cover the whole variety of existing medical cohorts that can be considered large. In terms of dimension, for example, the concept of “large” highly depends on the context, and as absolute numerical thresholds were selected, this could be found to be arbitrary. Despite that, to approach this, different thresholds were defined for population and clinical cohorts, and even for rare disease cohorts. However, and as commented, this definition was only intended to be a working definition and can also be modified over the course of the project.

The conduction of a Delphi study allowed to recover the views of an important number of experts in terms of areas of unmet medical needs and opportunities for improved medical care in an organized manner. Moreover, the majority of the experts presented more than 20 years of expertise in the field. Another strength of the current Delphi study is that it incorporated opinions of a broad spectrum of experts in terms of their professional roles, including researchers in various fields, physicians, or patient associations, among others, which allowed the collection of different viewpoints. Regarding expert characteristics, it was balanced in terms of gender, included experts from all age ranges and with great representativeness across Europe, as experts from 22 countries were included. The inclusion of experts from this wide variety of countries allowed to have a broader vision on the European landscape. Moreover, the methodology used in the Delphi study and its anonymity prevents biased responses and encourages honesty. Despite all that, a potential bias of experts towards their own field of expertise cannot be discarded. Another limitation of the current Delphi study is that the expected number of 100 experts was not reached. Expert identification and follow-up were challenging as the study started in July, during a holiday period in which many professionals are away.

Another strength of the current work was to perform a scoping review for the analysis of the existing large medical cohort in Europe. This selected methodology is appropriate to the explorative research goal, as it enabled to map existing evidence in this field. However, it did not allow to assess the quality of the identified studies.

Even though one of the main aims of the current work was to carry out a comprehensive search of existing efforts within the LMedC cohort landscape in Europe due to the high amount of existing cohort studies it was not possible to address the whole range of medical areas. In this sense, we took advantage of the results from the conducted Delphi study, which identified the areas of unmet medical needs and allowed to direct the scoping review to the three disorders of main interest regarding the medical cohort landscape in Europe. This approach allowed to conduct a deeper analysis of these areas and of their existing cohorts. In a similar manner, due to the elevated amount of results, the search had to be restricted to the five last years.

In terms of results, it is also worth noting that a limitation of the current work was the selection of the delimitation of the concept “large”. As strict thresholds were defined (more than 10000 participants in population cohorts and 1000 for clinical cohorts), this did not allow to incorporate cohorts with a slightly smaller sample size, such as 9780, for example. Similarly, we noted that with these sample size criteria we had to exclude an elevated number of cohorts, some of which were even considered to be large for the authors of the studies. As stated, these thresholds are arbitrary, and while it was necessary to define them to have a working definition and be able to start systematically analysing existing cohorts, these are not set in stone and may need to be revised for future work.

Finally, another strength of this work is that it finalised with an analysis of current needs and recommendations consulting experts in the field. This gives closure to the conducted general analysis of existing LMedC, identifying other key issues to address and providing starting points and ideas to continue the project.

8. REFERENCES

Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation. (2024). *Global Burden of Disease Study 2021 (GBD 2021)*. University of Washington. Retrieved from <https://www.healthdata.org>

Guo, J., Garratt, A., & Hill, A. (2022). Worldwide rates of diagnosis and effective treatment for cystic fibrosis. *Journal of Cystic Fibrosis*, 21(3), 456-462. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcf.2022.01.009>

Niu, H., Álvarez-Álvarez, I., Guillén-Grimma, F., & Aguinaga-Ontoso, I. (2016). Prevalence and incidence of Alzheimer's disease in Europe: A meta-analysis. *Neurología (English Edition)*, 31(4), 234-242. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nrleng.2016.02.009>

Pavlik, V. N., Burnham, S. C., Kass, J. S., Helmer, C., Palmqvist, S., Vassilaki, M., Dartigues, J. F., Hansson, O., Masters, C. L., Pérès, K., Petersen, R. C., Stomrud, E., Butler, L., Coloma, P. M., Teitsma, X. M., Doody, R., Sano, M., & CONCORD-AD investigators (2022). Connecting Cohorts to Diminish Alzheimer's Disease (CONCORD-AD): A Report of an International Research Collaboration Network. *Journal of Alzheimer's disease : JAD*, 85(1), 31–45. <https://doi.org/10.3233/JAD-210525>

Peters, M. D., Godfrey, C. M., Khalil, H., McInerney, P., Parker, D., & Soares, C. B. (2015). Guidance for conducting systematic scoping reviews. *International journal of evidence-based healthcare*, 13(3), 141–146. <https://doi.org/10.1097/XEB.0000000000000050>

Peters MDJ, Godfrey C, McInerney P, Munn Z, Tricco AC, Khalil, H. Scoping Reviews (2020). Aromataris E, Lockwood C, Porritt K, Pilla B, Jordan Z, editors. *JBIM Manual for Evidence Synthesis*. JBI; 2024. Available from: <https://synthesismanual.jbi.global>. <https://doi.org/10.46658/JBIMES-24-09>

Tricco, A. C., Lillie, E., Zarin, W., O'Brien, K. K., Colquhoun, H., Levac, D., Moher, D., Peters, M. D. J., Horsley, T., Weeks, L., Hempel, S., Akl, E. A., Chang, C., McGowan, J., Stewart, L., Hartling, L., Aldcroft, A., Wilson, M. G., Garritty, C., Lewin, S., ... Straus, S. E. (2018). PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR): Checklist and Explanation. *Annals of internal medicine*, 169(7), 467–473. <https://doi.org/10.7326/M18-0850>

Waithira, N., Mutinda, B., & Cheah, P. Y. (2019). Data management and sharing policy: the first step towards promoting data sharing. *BMC medicine*, 17(1), 80. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-019-1315-8>

Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J. W., da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., ... Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific data*, 3, 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

World Health Organization. (2021, March 8). *Endometriosis*. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/endometriosis#:~:text=Key%20facts,age%20women%20and%20girls%20globally>.

9.APPENDICES

Appendix A: Delphi Study Round 1 Questionnaire

GAP ANALYSIS - LMedC - DELPHI STUDY ROUND 1

Start of Block: Default Question Block

Q1 Do you have any feedback regarding our definition of Large Medical Cohorts (LMedC)?

A medical cohort refers to a group of individuals with a shared condition, characteristic or exposure who might be followed over time to collect extensive health-related data and/or biological materials for current and future health research. The data and biological materials collected from a medical cohort are stored as databank and/or biobank collections. In this project, we neither consider interventional clinical trials nor databanks based on health registries without specific follow-up as medical cohorts. We consider a medical cohort as "large": A clinical cohort (observational) comprising over 1000 participants selected for a health condition; or A rare disease cohort comprising over 0,5-1% (as a rough guideline) of the total disease population of the country; or A population cohort comprising over 10,000 participants.

Yes (1) _____

No (2)

Page Break

Q1 Please list the **three main diseases** that you believe have a deficiency in available research data, contributing to unmet medical needs in Europe?

Disease 1 (1) _____

Disease 2 (2) _____

Disease 3 (3) _____

Page Break _____

End of Block: Default Question Block

Start of Block: Disease 1

Q21 There are effective treatments available for $\${Q1/ChoiceTextEntryValue/1}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
 - Disagree (2)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (3)
 - Agree (4)
 - Strongly agree (5)
-

Q22 These treatments are accessible for treating people with $\${Q1/ChoiceTextEntryValue/1}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
 - Disagree (2)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (3)
 - Agree (4)
 - Strongly agree (5)
-

Q23 There are proven strategies to prevent $\${Q1/ChoiceTextEntryValue/1}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
 - Disagree (2)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (3)
 - Agree (4)
 - Strongly agree (5)
-

Q24 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\${Q1/ChoiceTextEntryValue/1}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
 - Disagree (2)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (3)
 - Agree (4)
 - Strongly agree (5)
-

Q25 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceTextEntryValue/1\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
 - Disagree (2)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (3)
 - Agree (4)
 - Strongly agree (5)
 - Strongly disagree (6)
 - Disagree (7)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (8)
 - Agree (9)
 - Strongly agree (10)
-

Q26 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 1

Start of Block: Disease 2

Q8 There are effective treatments available for $\${Q1/ChoiceTextEntryValue/2}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
 - Disagree (2)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (3)
 - Agree (4)
 - Strongly agree (5)
-

Q9 These treatments are accessible for treating the people with $\${Q1/ChoiceTextEntryValue/2}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
 - Disagree (2)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (3)
 - Agree (4)
 - Strongly agree (5)
-

Q10 There are proven strategies to prevent $\${Q1/ChoiceTextEntryValue/2}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
 - Disagree (2)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (3)
 - Agree (4)
 - Strongly agree (5)
-

Q11 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\${Q1/ChoiceTextEntryValue/2}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
 - Disagree (2)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (3)
 - Agree (4)
 - Strongly agree (5)
-

Q12 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceTextEntryValue/2\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
 - Disagree (2)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (3)
 - Agree (4)
 - Strongly agree (5)
 - Strongly disagree (6)
 - Disagree (7)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (8)
 - Agree (9)
 - Strongly agree (10)
-

Q13 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 2

Start of Block: Disease 3

Q14 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q1/ChoiceTextEntryValue/3\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
 - Disagree (2)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (3)
 - Agree (4)
 - Strongly agree (5)
-

Q15 These treatments are accessible for treating people with $\{Q1/ChoiceTextEntryValue/3\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
 - Disagree (2)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (3)
 - Agree (4)
 - Strongly agree (5)
-

Q16 There are proven strategies to prevent $\${Q1/ChoiceTextEntryValue/3}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
 - Disagree (2)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (3)
 - Agree (4)
 - Strongly agree (5)
-

Q17 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\${Q1/ChoiceTextEntryValue/3}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
 - Disagree (2)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (3)
 - Agree (4)
 - Strongly agree (5)
-

Q18 You believe that $\{Q1/ChoiceTextEntryValue/3\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
 - Disagree (2)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (3)
 - Agree (4)
 - Strongly agree (5)
 - Strongly disagree (6)
 - Disagree (7)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (8)
 - Agree (9)
 - Strongly agree (10)
-

Q19 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 3

Start of Block: List DALYs

Q20 Within the list below, please select **three main diseases** that you believe have a deficiency in available research data, contributing to unmet medical needs in Europe? *This list of diseases has been compiled based on the results of the **first round** of the Delphi study. The objective is to identify the three diseases or areas that, in your view, demonstrate*

a significant deficiency in available research data, thereby contributing to unmet medical needs within Europe.

- Ischemic heart disease (10.75% of total DALYs) (1)
- Stroke (6.30% of total DALYs) (2)
- Low back pain (4.15% of total DALYs) (3)
- Tracheal, bronchus and lung cancer (3.09% of total DALYs) (4)
- Diabetes mellitus (2.64% of total DALYs) (5)
- Falls (2.47% of total DALYs) (6)
- Alzheimer's disease and other dementias (2.37% of total DALYs) (7)
- Depressive disorders (2.06% of total DALYs) (8)
- Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (1.90% of total DALYs) (9)
- Colon and rectum cancer (1.88% of total DALYs) (10)
- Cirrhosis and other chronic liver diseases (1.84% of total DALYs) (11)
- Headache disorders (1.80% of total DALYs) (12)
- Age-related and other hearing loss (1.64% of total DALYs) (13)
- Anxiety disorders (1.63% of total DALYs) (14)

- Cardiomyopathy and myocarditis (1.31% of total DALYs) (15)
- Breast cancer (1.23% of total DALYs) (16)
- Chronic kidney disease (1.13% of total DALYs) (17)
- Oral disorders (1.12% of total DALYs) (18)
- Hypertensive heart disease (1.10% of total DALYs) (19)
- Pancreatic cancer (0.97% of total DALYs) (20)

End of Block: List DALYs

Start of Block: Disease 1

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Ischemic heart disease (10.75% of total DALYs)

Q46 There are effective treatments available for \${Q20/ChoiceDescription/1}

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Ischemic heart disease (10.75% of total DALYs)

Q47 These treatments are accessible for treating people with \${Q20/ChoiceDescription/1}

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Ischemic heart disease (10.75% of total DALYs)

Q48 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/1\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Ischemic heart disease (10.75% of total DALYs)

Q49 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/1\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
 - Disagree (2)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (3)
 - Agree (4)
 - Strongly agree (5)
-

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Ischemic heart disease (10.75% of total DALYs)

Q50 You believe $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/1\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)
- Strongly disagree (6)
- Disagree (7)
- Neither agree nor disagree (8)
- Agree (9)
- Strongly agree (10)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Ischemic heart disease (10.75% of total DALYs)

Q149 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 1

Start of Block: Disease 2

Page Break

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Stroke (6.30% of total DALYs)

Q51 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/2\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Stroke (6.30% of total DALYs)

Q52 These treatments are accessible for treating people with $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/2\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Stroke (6.30% of total DALYs)

Q53 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/2\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Stroke (6.30% of total DALYs)

Q54 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/2\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Stroke (6.30% of total DALYs)

Q55 You believe $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/2\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)
- Strongly disagree (6)
- Disagree (7)
- Neither agree nor disagree (8)
- Agree (9)
- Strongly agree (10)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Stroke (6.30% of total DALYs)

Q150 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 2

Start of Block: Disease 3

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Low back pain (4.15% of total DALYs)

Q40 There are effective treatments available for $\${Q20/ChoiceDescription/3}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Low back pain (4.15% of total DALYs)

Q41 These treatments are accessible for treating people with $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/3\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Low back pain (4.15% of total DALYs)

Q42 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/3\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Low back pain (4.15% of total DALYs)

Q43 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of [\\${Q20/ChoiceDescription/3}](#)

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Low back pain (4.15% of total DALYs)

Q44 You believe $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/3\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)
- Strongly disagree (6)
- Disagree (7)
- Neither agree nor disagree (8)
- Agree (9)
- Strongly agree (10)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Low back pain (4.15% of total DALYs)

Q151 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 3

Start of Block: Disease 4

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Tracheal, bronchus and lung cancer (3.09% of total DALYs)

Q56 There are effective treatments available for $\${Q20/ChoiceDescription/4}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Tracheal, bronchus and lung cancer (3.09% of total DALYs)

Q57 These treatments are accessible for treating people with \${Q20/ChoiceDescription/4}

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Tracheal, bronchus and lung cancer (3.09% of total DALYs)

Q58 There are proven strategies to prevent \${Q20/ChoiceDescription/4}

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Tracheal, bronchus and lung cancer (3.09% of total DALYs)

Q59 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/4\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Tracheal, bronchus and lung cancer (3.09% of total DALYs)

Q60 You believe $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/4\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)
- Strongly disagree (6)
- Disagree (7)
- Neither agree nor disagree (8)
- Agree (9)
- Strongly agree (10)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Tracheal, bronchus and lung cancer (3.09% of total DALYs)

Q152 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 4

Start of Block: Disease 5

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Diabetes mellitus (2.64% of total DALYs)

Q63 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/5\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Diabetes mellitus (2.64% of total DALYs)

Q64 These treatments are accessible for treating people with \${Q20/ChoiceDescription/5}

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Diabetes mellitus (2.64% of total DALYs)

Q65 There are proven strategies to prevent \${Q20/ChoiceDescription/5}

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Diabetes mellitus (2.64% of total DALYs)

Q66 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of [\\${Q20/ChoiceDescription/5}](#)

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Diabetes mellitus (2.64% of total DALYs)

Q67 You believe $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/5\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)
- Strongly disagree (6)
- Disagree (7)
- Neither agree nor disagree (8)
- Agree (9)
- Strongly agree (10)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Diabetes mellitus (2.64% of total DALYs)

Q153 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 5

Start of Block: Disease 6

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Falls (2.47% of total DALYs)

Q68 There are effective treatments available for $\${Q20/ChoiceDescription/6}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Falls (2.47% of total DALYs)

Q69 These treatments are accessible for treating people with \${Q20/ChoiceDescription/6}

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Falls (2.47% of total DALYs)

Q70 There are proven strategies to prevent \${Q20/ChoiceDescription/6}

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Falls (2.47% of total DALYs)

Q71 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/6\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Falls (2.47% of total DALYs)

Q72 You believe $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/6\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)
- Strongly disagree (6)
- Disagree (7)
- Neither agree nor disagree (8)
- Agree (9)
- Strongly agree (10)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Falls (2.47% of total DALYs)

Q154 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 6

Start of Block: Disease 7

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Alzheimer's disease and other dementias (2.37% of total DALYs)

Q73 There are effective treatments available for $\${Q20/ChoiceDescription/7}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Alzheimer's disease and other dementias (2.37% of total DALYs)

Q74 These treatments are accessible for treating people with $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/7\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Alzheimer's disease and other dementias (2.37% of total DALYs)

Q75 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/7\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Alzheimer's disease and other dementias (2.37% of total DALYs)

Q76 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of [\\${Q20/ChoiceDescription/7}](#)

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Alzheimer's disease and other dementias (2.37% of total DALYs)

Q77 You believe $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/7\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)
- Strongly disagree (6)
- Disagree (7)
- Neither agree nor disagree (8)
- Agree (9)
- Strongly agree (10)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Alzheimer's disease and other dementias (2.37% of total DALYs)

Q155 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 7

Start of Block: Disease 8

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Depressive disorders (2.06% of total DALYs)

Q78 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/8\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Depressive disorders (2.06% of total DALYs)

Q79 These treatments are accessible for treating people with \${Q20/ChoiceDescription/8}

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Depressive disorders (2.06% of total DALYs)

Q80 There are proven strategies to prevent \${Q20/ChoiceDescription/8}

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Depressive disorders (2.06% of total DALYs)

Q81 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of [\\${Q20/ChoiceDescription/8}](#)

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

*If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... =
Depressive disorders (2.06% of total DALYs)*

Q82 You believe $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/8\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)
- Strongly disagree (6)
- Disagree (7)
- Neither agree nor disagree (8)
- Agree (9)
- Strongly agree (10)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Depressive disorders (2.06% of total DALYs)

Q156 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 8

Start of Block: Disease 9

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (1.90% of total DALYs)

Q83 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/9\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (1.90% of total DALYs)

Q84 These treatments are accessible for treating people with \${Q20/ChoiceDescription/9}

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (1.90% of total DALYs)

Q85 There are proven strategies to prevent \${Q20/ChoiceDescription/9}

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (1.90% of total DALYs)

Q86 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of [\\${Q20/ChoiceDescription/9}](#)

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (1.90% of total DALYs)

Q87 You believe $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/9\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)
- Strongly disagree (6)
- Disagree (7)
- Neither agree nor disagree (8)
- Agree (9)
- Strongly agree (10)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (1.90% of total DALYs)

Q157 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 9

Start of Block: Disease 10

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Colon and rectum cancer (1.88% of total DALYs)

Q88 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/10\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Colon and rectum cancer (1.88% of total DALYs)

Q89 These treatments are accessible for treating people with \${Q20/ChoiceDescription/10}

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Colon and rectum cancer (1.88% of total DALYs)

Q90 There are proven strategies to prevent \${Q20/ChoiceDescription/10}

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Colon and rectum cancer (1.88% of total DALYs)

Q91 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/10\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Colon and rectum cancer (1.88% of total DALYs)

Q92 You believe $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/10\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)
- Strongly disagree (6)
- Disagree (7)
- Neither agree nor disagree (8)
- Agree (9)
- Strongly agree (10)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Colon and rectum cancer (1.88% of total DALYs)

Q158 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 10

Start of Block: Disease 11

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Cirrhosis and other chronic liver diseases (1.84% of total DALYs)

Q93 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/11\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Cirrhosis and other chronic liver diseases (1.84% of total DALYs)

Q94 These treatments are accessible for treating people with $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/11\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Cirrhosis and other chronic liver diseases (1.84% of total DALYs)

Q95 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/11\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Cirrhosis and other chronic liver diseases (1.84% of total DALYs)

Q96 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of [\\${Q20/ChoiceDescription/11}](#)

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Cirrhosis and other chronic liver diseases (1.84% of total DALYs)

Q97 You believe $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/11\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)
- Strongly disagree (6)
- Disagree (7)
- Neither agree nor disagree (8)
- Agree (9)
- Strongly agree (10)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Cirrhosis and other chronic liver diseases (1.84% of total DALYs)

Q159 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 11

Start of Block: Disease 12

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Headache disorders (1.80% of total DALYs)

Q98 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/12\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Headache disorders (1.80% of total DALYs)

Q99 These treatments are accessible for treating people with $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/12\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Headache disorders (1.80% of total DALYs)

Q100 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/12\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Headache disorders (1.80% of total DALYs)

Q101 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/12\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Headache disorders (1.80% of total DALYs)

Q102 You believe $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/12\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)
- Strongly disagree (6)
- Disagree (7)
- Neither agree nor disagree (8)
- Agree (9)
- Strongly agree (10)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Headache disorders (1.80% of total DALYs)

Q160 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 12

Start of Block: Disease 13

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Age-related and other hearing loss (1.64% of total DALYs)

Q103 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/13\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Age-related and other hearing loss (1.64% of total DALYs)

Q104 These treatments are accessible for treating people with $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/13\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Age-related and other hearing loss (1.64% of total DALYs)

Q105 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/13\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Age-related and other hearing loss (1.64% of total DALYs)

Q106 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/13\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Age-related and other hearing loss (1.64% of total DALYs)

Q107 You believe $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/13\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)
- Strongly disagree (6)
- Disagree (7)
- Neither agree nor disagree (8)
- Agree (9)
- Strongly agree (10)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Age-related and other hearing loss (1.64% of total DALYs)

Q161 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 13

Start of Block: Disease 14

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Anxiety disorders (1.63% of total DALYs)

Q108 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/14\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Anxiety disorders (1.63% of total DALYs)

Q109 These treatments are accessible for treating people with [\\${Q20/ChoiceDescription/14}](#)

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Anxiety disorders (1.63% of total DALYs)

Q110 There are proven strategies to prevent [\\${Q20/ChoiceDescription/14}](#)

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Anxiety disorders (1.63% of total DALYs)

Q111 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/14\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Anxiety disorders (1.63% of total DALYs)

Q112 You believe $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/14\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)
- Strongly disagree (6)
- Disagree (7)
- Neither agree nor disagree (8)
- Agree (9)
- Strongly agree (10)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Anxiety disorders (1.63% of total DALYs)

Q162 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 14

Start of Block: Disease 15

Display This Question:

*If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... =
Cardiomyopathy and myocarditis (1.31% of total DALYs)*

Q113 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/15\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

*If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... =
Cardiomyopathy and myocarditis (1.31% of total DALYs)*

Q114 These treatments are accessible for treating people with $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/15\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Cardiomyopathy and myocarditis (1.31% of total DALYs)

Q115 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/15\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

*If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... =
Cardiomyopathy and myocarditis (1.31% of total DALYs)*

Q116 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/15\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

*If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... =
Cardiomyopathy and myocarditis (1.31% of total DALYs)*

Q117 You believe $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/15\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)
- Strongly disagree (6)
- Disagree (7)
- Neither agree nor disagree (8)
- Agree (9)
- Strongly agree (10)

Display This Question:

*If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... =
Cardiomyopathy and myocarditis (1.31% of total DALYs)*

Q163 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 15

Start of Block: Disease 16

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Breast cancer (1.23% of total DALYs)

Q118 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/16\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Breast cancer (1.23% of total DALYs)

Q119 These treatments are accessible for treating people with $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/16\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Breast cancer (1.23% of total DALYs)

Q120 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/16\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Breast cancer (1.23% of total DALYs)

Q121 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/16\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Breast cancer (1.23% of total DALYs)

Q122 You believe $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/16\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)
- Strongly disagree (6)
- Disagree (7)
- Neither agree nor disagree (8)
- Agree (9)
- Strongly agree (10)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Breast cancer (1.23% of total DALYs)

Q164 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 16

Start of Block: Disease 17

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Chronic kidney disease (1.13% of total DALYs)

Q123 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/17\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Chronic kidney disease (1.13% of total DALYs)

Q124 These treatments are accessible for treating people with $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/17\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Chronic kidney disease (1.13% of total DALYs)

Q125 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/17\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Chronic kidney disease (1.13% of total DALYs)

Q126 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/17\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Chronic kidney disease (1.13% of total DALYs)

Q127 You believe $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/17\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)
- Strongly disagree (6)
- Disagree (7)
- Neither agree nor disagree (8)
- Agree (9)
- Strongly agree (10)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Chronic kidney disease (1.13% of total DALYs)

Q165 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 17

Start of Block: Disease 18

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Oral disorders (1.12% of total DALYs)

Q128 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/18\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Oral disorders (1.12% of total DALYs)

Q129 These treatments are accessible for treating people with $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/18\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Oral disorders (1.12% of total DALYs)

Q130 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/18\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Oral disorders (1.12% of total DALYs)

Q131 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/18\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Oral disorders (1.12% of total DALYs)

Q132 You believe $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/18\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)
- Strongly disagree (6)
- Disagree (7)
- Neither agree nor disagree (8)
- Agree (9)
- Strongly agree (10)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Oral disorders (1.12% of total DALYs)

Q166 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 18

Start of Block: Disease 19

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Hypertensive heart disease (1.10% of total DALYs)

Q133 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/19\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Hypertensive heart disease (1.10% of total DALYs)

Q134 These treatments are accessible for treating people with $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/19\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Hypertensive heart disease (1.10% of total DALYs)

Q135 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/19\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Hypertensive heart disease (1.10% of total DALYs)

Q136 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/19\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Hypertensive heart disease (1.10% of total DALYs)

Q137 You believe $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/19\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)
- Strongly disagree (6)
- Disagree (7)
- Neither agree nor disagree (8)
- Agree (9)
- Strongly agree (10)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Hypertensive heart disease (1.10% of total DALYs)

Q167 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 19

Start of Block: Disease 20

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Pancreatic cancer (0.97% of total DALYs)

Q138 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/20\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Pancreatic cancer (0.97% of total DALYs)

Q139 These treatments are accessible for treating people with $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/20\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Pancreatic cancer (0.97% of total DALYs)

Q140 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/20\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Pancreatic cancer (0.97% of total DALYs)

Q141 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/20\}$

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Pancreatic cancer (0.97% of total DALYs)

Q142 You believe $\{Q20/ChoiceDescription/20\}$ requires the following types of cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly disagree (1)
- Disagree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Agree (4)
- Strongly agree (5)
- Strongly disagree (6)
- Disagree (7)
- Neither agree nor disagree (8)
- Agree (9)
- Strongly agree (10)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Pancreatic cancer (0.97% of total DALYs)

Q168 Could you please motivate your answer(s)? (Optional)

End of Block: Disease 20

Start of Block: Open feedback

Q28 What do you think should be done on an European level to improve the availability of cohorts to address unmet medical needs?

Q29 Do you have feedback, opinions, or suggestions regarding the use of large medical cohorts in improving medical care for the diseases you mentioned earlier? *Please feel free to share any insights or recommendations you believe could enhance research and patient outcomes in the selected fields.*

End of Block: Open feedback

Start of Block: Expert information

Q30 What is your sex?

- Male (1)
- Female (2)
- Other (3)
- Prefer not to say (4)

Q32 What is your age range?

- 18-35 years (1)
 - 35-44 years (2)
 - 45-54 years (3)
 - 55-64 years (4)
 - 65 and above (5)
-

Q34 What is your profession?

- Physician (1)
 - Citizen or patient association (2)
 - Practicing health professional in primary care (3)
 - Health policy professional / Policy maker (4)
 - Public health professional (5)
 - Health care manager (6)
 - Clinical researcher (7)
 - Epidemiology or public health researcher (8)
 - Translational researcher (9)
 - Cohort researcher (10)
 - Other, please specify: (11)
-

Q35 How many years have you been actively engaged in this field?

- 1-5 years (1)
 - 6-10 years (2)
 - 11-15 years (3)
 - 16-20 years (4)
 - >21 years (5)
-

Q36 In which country are you professionally active?

▼ Albania (1) ... Other, please specify (51)

End of Block: Expert information

Appendix B: Delphi Study Round 2 Questionnaire

DELPHI STUDY - Round 2

Start of Block: PRINCIPAL QUESTION

Q1 Within the list below, please select **three main diseases** that you believe have a deficiency in available research data, contributing to unmet medical needs in Europe? *This list of diseases has been compiled based on the results of the **first round** of the Delphi study. The objective is to identify the three diseases or areas that, in your view, demonstrate*

a significant deficiency in available research data, thereby contributing to unmet medical needs within Europe.

- Mental disorders (depression, ADHD, anxiety...) (1)
- Low back pain (2)
- Headache disorders (3)
- Alzheimer's disease and other dementias (4)
- Endometriosis (5)
- Diabetes mellitus (6)
- Rare diseases (15)
- Pancreatic cancer (7)
- Age-related and other hearing loss (8)
- Stroke (9)
- Ischemic heart disease (10)
- Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (11)
- Hypertensive heart disorder (12)
- Cystic fibrosis (13)

Falls (14)

End of Block: PRINCIPAL QUESTION

Start of Block: DISEASE 1

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Mental disorders (depression, ADHD, anxiety...)

Q2 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/1\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Mental disorders (depression, ADHD, anxiety...)

Q3 These treatments are accessible for treating people with $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/1\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Mental disorders (depression, ADHD, anxiety...)

Q4 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/1\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Mental disorders (depression, ADHD, anxiety...)

Q5 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/1\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Mental disorders (depression, ADHD, anxiety...)

Q6 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/1\}$ require **population** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Mental disorders (depression, ADHD, anxiety...)

Q7 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/1\}$ require **clinical cohort** studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

End of Block: DISEASE 1

Start of Block: DISEASE 2

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Low back pain

Q8 There are effective treatments available for \${Q1/ChoiceDescription/2}

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Low back pain

Q9 These treatments are accessible for treating people with \${Q1/ChoiceDescription/2}

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Low back pain

Q10 There are proven strategies to prevent \${Q1/ChoiceDescription/2}

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Low back pain

Q11 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of \${Q1/ChoiceDescription/2}

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Low back pain

Q12 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/2\}$ require **population** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Low back pain

Q13 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/2\}$ require **clinical** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

End of Block: DISEASE 2

Start of Block: DISEASE 3

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Headache disorders

Q14 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/3\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
 - Agree (2)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (3)
 - Disagree (4)
 - Strongly disagree (5)
-

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Headache disorders

Q15 These treatments are accessible for treating people with $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/3\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Headache disorders

Q16 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/3\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Headache disorders

Q17 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/3\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Headache disorders

Q18 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/3\}$ require **population** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Headache disorders

Q19 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/3\}$ require **clinical** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

End of Block: DISEASE 3

Start of Block: DISEASE 4

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Alzheimer's disease and other dementias

Q20 There are effective treatments available for $\${Q1/ChoiceDescription/4}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Alzheimer's disease and other dementias

Q21 These treatments are accessible for treating people with \${Q1/ChoiceDescription/4}

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Alzheimer's disease and other dementias

Q22 There are proven strategies to prevent \${Q1/ChoiceDescription/4}

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Alzheimer's disease and other dementias

Q23 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/4\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Alzheimer's disease and other dementias

Q24 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/4\}$ require population cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Alzheimer's disease and other dementias

Q25 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/4\}$ require **clinical** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

End of Block: DISEASE 4

Start of Block: DISEASE 5

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Endometriosis

Q26 There are effective treatments available for \${Q1/ChoiceDescription/5}

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Endometriosis

Q27 These treatments are accessible for treating people with \${Q1/ChoiceDescription/5}

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Endometriosis

Q28 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/5\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Endometriosis

Q29 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/5\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Endometriosis

Q30 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/5\}$ require **population** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Endometriosis

Q31 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/5\}$ require **clinical** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

End of Block: DISEASE 5

Start of Block: DISEASE 6

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Diabetes mellitus

Q32 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/6\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
 - Agree (2)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (3)
 - Disagree (4)
 - Strongly disagree (5)
-

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Diabetes mellitus

Q33 These treatments are accessible for treating people with $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/6\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Diabetes mellitus

Q34 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/6\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Diabetes mellitus

Q35 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/6\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Diabetes mellitus

Q36 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/6\}$ require **population** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Diabetes mellitus

Q37 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/6\}$ require **clinical** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

End of Block: DISEASE 6

Start of Block: DISEASE 7

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Pancreatic cancer

Q38 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/7\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Pancreatic cancer

Q39 These treatments are accessible for treating people with $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/7\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Pancreatic cancer

Q40 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/7\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Pancreatic cancer

Q41 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/7\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Pancreatic cancer

Q42 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/7\}$ require **population** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Pancreatic cancer

Q43 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/7\}$ require **clinical** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

End of Block: DISEASE 7

Start of Block: DISEASE 8

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Age-related and other hearing loss

Q52 There are effective treatments available for \${Q1/ChoiceDescription/8}

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Age-related and other hearing loss

Q60 These treatments are accessible for treating people with \${Q1/ChoiceDescription/8}

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Age-related and other hearing loss

Q68 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/8\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Age-related and other hearing loss

Q76 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/8\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Age-related and other hearing loss

Q84 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/8\}$ require **population** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Age-related and other hearing loss

Q92 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/8\}$ require **clinical** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

End of Block: DISEASE 8

Start of Block: DISEASE 9

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Stroke

Q53 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/9\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
 - Agree (2)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (3)
 - Disagree (4)
 - Strongly disagree (5)
-

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Stroke

Q61 These treatments are accessible for treating people with $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/9\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Stroke

Q69 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/9\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Stroke

Q77 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/9\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Stroke

Q85 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/9\}$ require **population** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Stroke

Q93 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/9\}$ require **clinical** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

End of Block: DISEASE 9

Start of Block: DISEASE 10

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Ischemic heart disease

Q54 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/10\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Ischemic heart disease

Q62 These treatments are accessible for treating people with $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/10\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Ischemic heart disease

Q70 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/10\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Ischemic heart disease

Q78 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/10\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Ischemic heart disease

Q86 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/10\}$ require **population** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Ischemic heart disease

Q94 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/10\}$ require **clinical** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

End of Block: DISEASE 10

Start of Block: DISEASE 11

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Q55 There are effective treatments available for \${Q1/ChoiceDescription/11}

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Q63 These treatments are accessible for treating people with \${Q1/ChoiceDescription/11}

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Q71 There are proven strategies to prevent \${Q1/ChoiceDescription/11}

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

*If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... =
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease*

Q79 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of \${Q1/ChoiceDescription/11}

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Q87 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/11\}$ require **population** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Q95 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/11\}$ require **clinical** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

End of Block: DISEASE 11

Start of Block: DISEASE 12

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Hypertensive heart disorder

Q56 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/12\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
 - Agree (2)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (3)
 - Disagree (4)
 - Strongly disagree (5)
-

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Hypertensive heart disorder

Q64 These treatments are accessible for treating people with $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/12\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Hypertensive heart disorder

Q72 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/12\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Hypertensive heart disorder

Q80 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/12\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Hypertensive heart disorder

Q88 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/12\}$ require **population** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Hypertensive heart disorder

Q96 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/12\}$ require **clinical** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

End of Block: DISEASE 12

Start of Block: DISEASE 13

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Cystic fibrosis

Q57 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/13\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Cystic fibrosis

Q65 These treatments are accessible for treating people with \${Q1/ChoiceDescription/13}

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Cystic fibrosis

Q73 There are proven strategies to prevent \${Q1/ChoiceDescription/13}

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Cystic fibrosis

Q81 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/13\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Cystic fibrosis

Q89 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/13\}$ require **population** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Cystic fibrosis

Q97 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/12\}$ require **clinical** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

End of Block: DISEASE 13

Start of Block: DISEASE 14

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Falls

Q58 There are effective treatments available for \${Q1/ChoiceDescription/14}

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Falls

Q66 These treatments are accessible for treating people with \${Q1/ChoiceDescription/14}

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Falls

Q74 There are proven strategies to prevent \${Q1/ChoiceDescription/14}

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Falls

Q82 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of \${Q1/ChoiceDescription/14}

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Falls

Q90 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/14\}$ require **population** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Falls

Q98 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/14\}$ require **clinical** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

End of Block: DISEASE 14

Start of Block: DISEASE 15

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Rare diseases

Q59 There are effective treatments available for $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/15\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
 - Agree (2)
 - Neither agree nor disagree (3)
 - Disagree (4)
 - Strongly disagree (5)
-

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Rare diseases

Q67 These treatments are accessible for treating people with $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/15\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Rare diseases

Q75 There are proven strategies to prevent $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/15\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Rare diseases

Q83 There is a need for large medical cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention of $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/15\}$

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Rare diseases

Q91 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/15\}$ require **population** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

Display This Question:

If Within the list below, please select three main diseases that you believe have a deficiency in av... = Rare diseases

Q99 You believe $\{Q1/ChoiceDescription/15\}$ require **clinical** cohort studies to enhance/improve treatment and prevention

- Strongly agree (1)
- Agree (2)
- Neither agree nor disagree (3)
- Disagree (4)
- Strongly disagree (5)

End of Block: DISEASE 15

Start of Block: EXPERT INFORMATION

Q44 Have you participated to the 1st Round of this Delphi study?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

Display This Question:

If Have you participated to the 1st Round of this Delphi study? = No

Q45 What is your sex?

- Male (1)
- Female (2)
- Other (3)
- Prefer not to say (4)

Display This Question:

If Have you participated to the 1st Round of this Delphi study? = No

Q46 What is your age range?

- 18-35 years (1)
- 36-44 years (2)
- 45-54 years (3)
- 55-64 years (4)
- 65 years and above (5)

Display This Question:

If Have you participated to the 1st Round of this Delphi study? = No

Q47 What is your profession?

- Physician (1)
 - Citizen or patient association (2)
 - Practicing health professional in primary care (3)
 - Health policy professional / Policy maker (4)
 - Public health professional (5)
 - Health care manager (6)
 - Clinical researcher (7)
 - Epidemiology or public health researcher (8)
 - Translational researcher (9)
 - Cohort researcher (10)
 - Other, please specify (11)
-

Display This Question:

If Have you participated to the 1st Round of this Delphi study? = No

Q48 How many years have you been actively engaged in this field?

- 1-5 years (1)
- 6-10 years (2)
- 11-15 years (3)
- 16-20 years (4)
- 21 years and above (5)

Display This Question:

If Have you participated to the 1st Round of this Delphi study? = No

Q49 In which country are you professionally active?

▼ Albania (1) ... Other, please specify (50)

End of Block: EXPERT INFORMATION

Start of Block: NOMINAL INTERVIEWS

Q100 *As part of our research, we are conducting online nominal interviews (10-15 minutes) with experts to define the final areas of unmet medical needs that could benefit from large*

medical cohorts. Would you be interested in participating in one of these nominal group interviews?

- Yes, I would like to participate (1)
- No, I am not interested at this time (2)
- Maybe, I would need more information (3)

End of Block: NOMINAL INTERVIEWS

Start of Block: FUTURE COLLABORATION

Q50 May we contact you in the future regarding the INTEGRATE-LMedC project, specifically for inquiries related to your preferences for tools and services provided by a European large medical cohort research infrastructure?

- Yes, I agree to be contacted (1)
 - No, I do not wish to be contacted (2)
-

Q51 May we use your name in any future publications of the survey results?

- Yes, I consent to the use of my name (1)
- No, I prefer to remain anonymous (2)

End of Block: FUTURE COLLABORATION

Appendix D: Data extraction results from the scoping review.

Table 10 – Data extraction results from studies using population cohorts in depression.

Name of Cohort Study	Title of manuscript	Year of publication	Study Design	Country	Sample size	Type of population	Age range of population	Frequency of follow-up	Number of follow-ups	Total Duration of follow-up
Seguimiento Universidad de Navarra cohort (SUN)	Lifestyles and the risk of depression in the "Seguimiento Universidad de Navarra" cohort	2019	prospective, dynamic and multipurpose study	Spain	14908		>18 years	irregular/as needed	single follow-up	10.4 years median
Irish Longitudinal Study on Ageing (TILDA)	Religious Attendance, Religious Importance, and the Pathways to Depressive Symptoms in Men and Women Aged 50 and Over Living in Ireland	2019	nationally representative longitudinal study	Ireland	6759	general population (country representative)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	8 years
NA	Child maltreatment, peer victimization, and social anxiety in adulthood: a cross-sectional study in a treatment-seeking sample	2019	cross-sectional multi centre study	Germany	1091	general population (country representative)	>18 years		single follow-up	
NA	Repetitive negative thinking as a mediator in prospective cross-disorder associations between anxiety and depression	2019	general prospective cohort study	Netherlands	1859	general population (country representative)	>18 years	more than 1 year and	multiple follow-ups	9 years

	disorders and their symptoms							less than 5 years		
Netherlands Study of Depression and Anxiety	Longitudinal Association Between Depression and Inflammatory Markers: Results From the Netherlands Study of Depression and Anxiety	2019	case-cohort study	Netherlands	2799	general population (country representative)	all ages	irregular/as needed	cross-sectional	6 years
data from Survey of Health, Ageing, and Retirement in Europe (SHARE)	Religiousness and depressive symptoms in Europeans: findings from the Survey of Health, Ageing, and Retirement in Europe	2019	other	Europe	23864	general population (geographic region)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	8 to 9 years
Data originate from Swedish National March Cohort study (SNMC)	Prospective associations between physical activity and clinician diagnosed major depressive disorder in adults: A 13-year cohort study	2019	general prospective cohort study	Sweden	43863	general population (country representative)	>18 years		single follow-up	13 years
EDEN (Etude sur les déterminants pré et postnataux précoces du Développement et de la santé de l'ENfant) and ELFE (Etude Longitudinale Française depuis l'Enfance)	Domain-specific physical activity and sedentary behavior during pregnancy and postpartum depression risk in the French EDEN and ELFE cohorts	2019	birth or age-based cohort study	France	17283		>18 years		multiple follow-ups	12 months
data from Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE)	Course of depressive symptoms and associated factors in people aged 65+	2019	general prospective cohort study	Europe	23201	general population (country representative)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	single follow-up	2 years

	in Europe: A two-year follow-up									
Seguimiento Universidad de Navarra (SUN)	Use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, aspirin and the risk of depression: The “Seguimiento Universidad de Navarra (SUN)” cohort	2019	general prospective cohort study	Spain	13961	general population (country representative)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	average of 8.7 years
Subjects of the Northern Finland 1966 Birth Cohort (NFBC 1966)	Severe mood disorders and schizophrenia in the adult offspring of antenatally depressed mothers in the Northern Finland 1966 Birth Cohort: Relationship to parental severe mental disorder	2019	birth or age-based cohort study	Finland	12058	unselected, general population-based sample	>18 years	irregular/as needed		43 years
data from the Norwegian Nord-Trøndelag Health Study (HUNT)	Cross-sectional and longitudinal association of non-exercise estimated cardiorespiratory fitness with depression and anxiety in the general population: The HUNT study	2019	general prospective cohort study	Norway	26615	depression and anxiety	>18 years	more than 10 years	single follow-up	11 years
Norwegian Mother and Child Cohort	Does Prenatal Stress Amplify Effects of Postnatal Maternal Depressive and Anxiety Symptoms on Child Problem Behavior?	2019	general prospective cohort study	Norway	48497	general population (gender-specific group(s))	<18 years	irregular/as needed	multiple follow-ups	6 years
Constances	Long-term effects of compulsory schooling on physical, mental and	2019	retrospectively constructed prospective cohort study	France	18928	general population (country representative)	>18 years		cross-sectional	

	cognitive ageing: a natural experiment									
Danish Work Environment Cohort Study (DWECS)	Impact of depressive symptoms on worklife expectancy: a longitudinal study on Danish employees	2019	retrospectively constructed prospective cohort study	Denmark	11967	general population (country representative)	>18 years		cross-sectional	
Psykisk Hälsa–Arbete–Relationer (PART) study	Moderate alcohol consumption and depression—a longitudinal population-based study in Sweden	2019	general prospective cohort study	Sweden	5087	general population (country representative)	all ages	irregular/as needed	multiple follow-ups	12 years
SHARE (Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe)	Childhood Socioeconomic Status and Late-Adulthood Mental Health: Results From the Survey on Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe	2019	multi-center cohort study	Europe	21989	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	2
Survey of Health, Ageing, and Retirement in Europe (SHARE)	A longitudinal study of neighbourhood conditions and depression in ageing European adults: Do the associations vary by exposure to childhood stressors?	2019	multi-center cohort study	Europe	10328	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	5
HAPIEE Study (Health, Alcohol, and Psychosocial factors In Eastern Europe)	The prospective relationship between social cohesion and depressive symptoms among older adults from Central and Eastern Europe	2019	general prospective cohort study	Europe	15438	general population (country representative)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	4

ALSPAC (Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children)	Associations between infant and toddler regulatory problems, childhood co-developing internalising and externalising trajectories, and adolescent depression, psychotic and borderline personality disorder symptoms	2019	birth or age-based cohort study	United Kingdom	14062	general population (age-specific group(s))	all ages	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	
Gazel Cohort Study	Depression, treatable cardiovascular risk factors and incident cardiac events in the Gazel cohort	2019	general prospective cohort study	France	10541	occupational groups	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	20 years
Child and Adolescent Twin Study in Sweden (CATSS)	Trends in childhood and adolescent internalizing symptoms: results from Swedish population based twin cohorts	2019	birth or age-based cohort study	Sweden	Multiple cohorts (about 30000 together)	general population (age-specific group(s))	<18 years	irregular/as needed	multiple follow-ups	6 years
Norwegian Mother and Child Cohort Study (MoBa)	Paternal antidepressant use as a negative control for maternal use: assessing familial confounding on gestational length and anxiety traits in offspring	2019	birth or age-based cohort study	Norway	70959	general population (age-specific group(s))	<18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	3 years
EPIC-Norfolk Study	Association between area deprivation and major depressive disorder in British men and women: a cohort study	2019	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	18571	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	from 7 to 12 months	multiple follow-ups	up to 7 years
Generation Scotland, UK Biobank	Insulin resistance: Genetic associations	2019	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	19994 + 331374	general population (country representative)	>18 years	irregular/as needed	cross-sectional	

	depression and cognition in population based cohorts									
Survey of Health, Ageing, and Retirement in Europe (SHARE)	Memory Deficits Precede Increases in Depressive Symptoms in Later Adulthood	2019	Multi center cohort study + age-based cohort study	Europe	107599	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	11 years
Netherlands Mental Health Survey and Incidence Study-2 (NEMESIS-2) Healthy Life in an Urban Setting study (HELIUS) Netherlands Twin Register (NTR) New Hoorn Study (HOORN) Longitudinal Aging Study Amsterdam (LASA) Netherlands Longitudinal Study on Hearing (NL-SH)) Generations Netherlands Study of Depression and Anxiety (NESDA)	Neighbourhood characteristics and prevalence and severity of depression: pooled analysis of eight Dutch cohort studies	2019	multi-center cohort study	Netherlands	32487	general population-based participants with a focus on mental health, ethnicity, genetics/twins, diabetes, ageing, hearing, pregnancy, and psychiatry	>18 years		cross-sectional	
the Nord-Trøndelag Health Study' (HUNT)	Loneliness as a risk factor for metabolic syndrome: results from the HUNT study	2019	general prospective cohort study	Norway	cohort = 120000 study = 26990	general population (geographic region)	>18 years	more than 10 years	single follow-up	13 years

<p>Amsterdam Born Children and their Development study (ABCD) the Generation R Study the German Infant Study on the influence of Nutrition Intervention PLUS environmental and genetic influences on allergy development (GINIplus) the Influence of life-style factors on the development of the immune system and allergies in East and West Germany Study (LISA) Polish Mother and Child Co-hort Study (REPRO_PL) Étude des Déterminants pré et postnatals du développement et de la santé de l'Enfant (EDEN) Genetica e Ambiente: Studio Prospettico dell'Infanzia in Italia (GASPII) and the Infancia y Medio Ambiente (INMA) project</p>	<p>Prenatal and postnatal exposure to air pollution and emotional and aggressive symptoms in children from 8 European birth cohort</p>	<p>2019</p>	<p>exposure specific + birth cohort study</p>	<p>Europe</p>	<p>study = 13182</p>	<p>general population (age-specific group(s))</p>	<p><18 years</p>		<p>cross-sectional</p>	
<p>UK Biobank (UKB)</p>	<p>The costs of negative affect attributable to alcohol consumption in later life: A within- between random</p>	<p>2019</p>	<p>exposure-specific cohort study</p>	<p>United Kingdom</p>	<p>study = 129437</p>	<p>general population (geographic region)</p>	<p>>18 years</p>	<p>irregular/as needed</p>	<p>cross-sectional</p>	

	longitudinal econometric model using UK Biobank									
Norwegian Mother and Child Cohort Study	Association of Maternal Use of Benzodiazepines and Z-Hypnotics During Pregnancy With Motor and Communication Skills and Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder Symptoms in Preschoolers	2019	exposure-specific cohort study	Norway	cohort = 41146 study = 36086	patients with a specific symptom	<18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	5 years
Gutenberg Health Study (GHS)	New onset of depression in aging women and men: contributions of social, psychological, behavioral, and somatic predictors in the community	2019	general prospective cohort study	Germany	study = 10036	general population (geographic region)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	single follow-up	5 years
The HUNT Study (Nord-Trøndelag Health Study)	Symptoms of Depression and Risk of Abdominal Aortic Aneurysm: A HUNT Study	2019	general prospective cohort study	Norway	59136	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 10 years	multiple follow-ups	Median 13 years (range 1 month-20 years)
Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE)	Importance of modelling decisions on estimating trajectories of depressive symptoms and co-morbid conditions in older adults: Longitudinal studies from ten European countries.	2019	general prospective cohort study	Europe	21253	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	Varies across countries; approximate follow-up period of 4–6 years.
English Longitudinal Study of Ageing (ELSA) and Health, Alcohol, and Psychosocial	Congruent relations between perceived neighbourhood social cohesion and depressive symptoms among older	2019	general prospective cohort study	Europe	26081	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and	multiple follow-ups	2-3 years

factors In Eastern Europe (HAPIEE) Study	European adults: An East-West analysis							less than 5 years		
Seguimiento Universidad de Navarra (SUN) cohort.	Does the MIND diet decrease depression risk? A comparison with Mediterranean diet in the SUN cohort.	2019	general prospective cohort study	Spain	15980	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	10.4 years (median).
PART Study (Psykisk hälsa, Arbete och Relationer: Mental Health, Work, and Relationships).	Does depressed persons with non-cardiovascular morbidity have a higher risk of CVD? A population-based cohort study in Sweden	2019	general prospective cohort study	Sweden	10074	general population (geographic region)	>18 years	more than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	14 years
Child and Adolescent Twin Study in Sweden (CATSS) and Netherlands Twin Register (NTR)	Anxiety at age 15 predicts psychiatric diagnoses and suicidal ideation in late adolescence and young adulthood: results from two longitudinal studies	2019	general prospective cohort study	Europe	14,106 (Sweden); 9,211 (Netherlands)	general population (age-specific group(s))	<18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	6 years (Sweden: up to 21 years of age)
NutriNet-Santé cohort study	Prospective association between ultra-processed food consumption and incident depressive symptoms in the French NutriNet-Santé cohort	2019	general prospective cohort study	France	26730	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	from 1 to 6 months	multiple follow-ups	5.4 years (mean follow-up duration)
Gutenberg Health Study (GHS)	Income and education predict elevated depressive symptoms in the general population	2019	general prospective cohort study	Germany	12484	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	single follow-up	2.5 years

English Longitudinal Study of Ageing (ELSA)	Joint trajectories of spousal social support and depressive symptoms in older age	2019	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	7171	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	8 years
Understanding Society: The UK Household Longitudinal Study (UKHLS)	Long work hours, weekend working and depressive symptoms in men and women: Findings from a UK population-based study	2019	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	23,403 participants (11,215 men and 12,188 women)	general population (country representative)	all ages	irregular/as needed	multiple follow-ups	2 years
Platform for Research Online to investigate Genetics and Cognition in Ageing Study	Temporal Relationship Between Depressive Symptoms and Cognition in Mid and Late Life: A Longitudinal Cohort Study	2020	birth or age-based cohort study	United Kingdom	11855	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	from 7 to 12 months	single follow-up	1 year
Etude Longitudinale Française depuis l'Enfance (ELFE)	Informal and formal social support during pregnancy and joint maternal and paternal postnatal depression: Data from the French representative ELFE cohort study	2020	birth or age-based cohort study	France	12350	general population (country representative)	>18 years	irregular/as needed	multiple follow-ups	2 years
data from Survey on Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE)	Changes in depressive symptoms of older adults in the Czech Republic	2020	general prospective cohort study	Czech Republic	2850		>18 years			
China Health and Retirement Longitudinal Study (CHARLS), English Longitudinal Study of Ageing (ELSA)	Do multigenerational living arrangements influence depressive symptoms in mid-late life? Cross-national findings from China and England	2020	retrospectively constructed prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	26632	general population (country representative)	>18 years	from 1 to 6 months	multiple follow-ups	2 years

Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE)	cross-sectional and prospective relationship between physical activity and depression symptoms	2020	retrospectively constructed prospective cohort study	Europe	32392	general population (country representative)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	single follow-up	4 years
Swedish Longitudinal Occupational Survey of Health (SLOSH)	The mediating effect of work-life interference on the relationship between work-time control and depressive symptoms	2020	general prospective cohort study	Sweden	26804	occupational groups	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	4
Northern Finland 1966 Birth Cohort	Antisocial and borderline personality disorders in the offspring of antenatally depressed mothers – a follow-up until mid-adulthood in the Northern Finland 1966 birth cohort	2020	birth or age-based cohort study	Finland	12058	general population (country representative)	all ages	more than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	49
Cognitive Function and Ageing Studies (CFAS I & II)	Changing prevalence and treatment of depression among older people over two decades	2020	General prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	7762	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	irregular/as needed	multiple follow-ups	
ALSPAC (Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children)	Associations of adverse childhood experiences with educational attainment and adolescent health and the role of family and socioeconomic factors: A prospective cohort study in the UK	2020	birth or age-based cohort study	United Kingdom	9959	general population (geographic region)	<18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	
Health and Retirement Study (HRS), ELSA, SHARE	The Longitudinal Associations of Perceived Neighborhood Disorder and Lack of Social Cohesion With Depression Among Adults Aged 50 Years or	2020	multi-center cohort study	Europe	32531	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	irregular/as needed	multiple follow-ups	5

	Older: An Individual-Participant-Data Meta-Analysis From 16 High-Income Countries									
Gutenberg Health Study (GHS)	Noise annoyance predicts symptoms of depression, anxiety and sleep disturbance 5 years later. Findings from the Gutenberg Health Study	2020	general prospective cohort study	Germany	11905	general population (geographic region)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	2
Longitudinal Aging Study Amsterdam (LASA), Danish Longitudinal Study of Ageing (DLSA), English Longitudinal Study of Ageing (ELSA), German Ageing Survey (DEAS)	Educational differences in the influence of health on early work exit among older workers	2020	multi-center cohort study	Europe	11727	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	Depending on a cohort	multiple follow-ups	Up to 15 years
Seguimiento Universidad de Navarra (SUN) Cohort Study	Dimensions of leisure-time physical activity and risk of depression in the "Seguimiento Universidad de Navarra" (SUN) prospective cohort	2020	exposure-specific cohort study	Spain	15488	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	irregular/as needed	multiple follow-ups	16 years
Bochum Optimism and Mental Health (BOOM) Study	Longitudinal prediction of positive and negative mental health in Germany, Russia, and China	2020	multi-center cohort study	Europe	14342	general population (age-specific group(s))	all ages	Depending on a cohort	multiple follow-ups	5 years
The Intensive Care Outcomes Network study (ICON)	Anxiety, depression and post-traumatic stress disorder management after critical illness: a UK multi-	2020	multi-center cohort study	United Kingdom	11726	patients undergoing a specific treatment	all ages	from 1 to 6 months	multiple follow-ups	12 months

	centre prospective cohort study									
The COVID-19 Social Study	Levels of Severity of Depressive Symptoms Among At-Risk Groups in the UK During the COVID-19 Pandemic	2020	retrospectively constructed prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	51417	general population (geographic region)	>18 years	monthly or more	continous follow-ups	2 weeks
Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children (ALSPAC)	Depressive symptoms and objectively measured physical activity and sedentary behaviour throughout adolescence: a prospective cohort study	2020	birth or age-based cohort study	United Kingdom	study = 14901	general population (age-specific group(s))	<18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	6 years
CHILD-SLEEP Cohort	Trajectories of mothers' and fathers' depressive symptoms from pregnancy to 24 months postpartum	2020	exposure-specific cohort study	Finland	study = 3299	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	irregular/as needed	multiple follow-ups	2.5 years
Constances cohort	Dietary Restrictions and Depressive Symptoms: Longitudinal Results from the Constances Cohort	2020	general prospective cohort study	France	cohort = >200000 study = 29337	general population (geographic region)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	single follow-up	3 years
Swedish Longitudinal Occupational Survey of Health (SLOSH)	Status incongruence in human service occupations and implications for mild-to-severe depressive symptoms and register-based sickness absence: A prospective cohort study	2020	general prospective cohort study	Sweden	3518	Swedish Working Pipulation	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	single follow-up	After two years (2014 and 2016)

Gutenberg Health Study (GHS).	Prevalence and new onset of depression and anxiety among participants with AMD in a European cohort.	2020	general prospective cohort study	Germany	11834	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	5 years
Seguimiento Universidad de Navarra (SUN) Project.	Ultra-processed food consumption and the incidence of depression in a Mediterranean cohort: the SUN Project.	2020	general prospective cohort study	Spain	14907	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	Median of 10.3 years.
Norwegian Mother, Father, and Child Cohort Study (MoBa)	How important are parents in the development of child anxiety and depression? A genomic analysis of parent-offspring trios in the Norwegian Mother Father and Child Cohort Study (MoBa)	2020	general prospective cohort study	Norway	11,598 parent-offspring trios (analyzed); 27,010 relative pairs (for pedigree modeling)	general population (age-specific group(s))	<18 years		cross-sectional	Not applicable
National Child Development Study (NCDS)	Adverse childhood experiences and adult mood problems: evidence from a five-decade prospective birth cohort	2020	birth or age-based cohort study	United Kingdom	12553	general population (age-specific group(s))	all ages	more than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	Birth to 50 years
Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE)	Late-life depression and the risk of dementia in 14 countries: a 10-year follow-up study from SHARE	2020	general prospective cohort study	Europe	16210	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	from 7 to 12 months	multiple follow-ups	10 years
Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE)	The role of pension contributions in explaining inequalities in depressive symptoms. Results from SHARE	2021	retrospectively constructed prospective cohort study	Europe	10248	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	irregular/as needed	cross-sectional	

data from e Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE)	Longitudinal associations between specific symptoms of depression: Network analysis in a prospective cohort study	2021	general prospective cohort study	Europe	72971	general population (country representative)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	13 years
data from three consecutive biennial surveys in 2010-2016, from the Swedish Longitudinal Occupational Survey of Health (SLOSH) and the Work Environment and Health in Denmark (WEHD) cohorts	Interrelationships between job demands, low back pain and depression: A four-way decomposition analysis of direct and indirect effects of job demands through mediation and/or interaction	2021	general prospective cohort study	Europe	26794	general population (country representative)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	12 years
Survey of Health, Aging and Retirement in Europe (SHARE)	Associations between self-rated health and depressive symptoms among older adults: Does age matter?	2021	retrospectively constructed prospective cohort study	Europe	28899	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	single follow-up	2 years
ALSPAC (Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children)	Breastfeeding, prenatal depression and children's IQ and behaviour: a test of a moderation model	2021	birth or age-based cohort study	United Kingdom	11096	general population (geographic region)	all ages	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	7
National Child Development Study (NCDS) and British Cohort Study (BCS)	Depressive symptoms during early adulthood and the development of physical multimorbidity in the UK: an observational cohort study	2021	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	15845	general population (country representative)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	20
IGEPEPP Study (Paris Maternity Departments)	Early- and late-onset postpartum depression exhibit distinct associated	2021	nested case-control study	France	3310	patients undergoing a specific treatment	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	3

	factors: the IGEDEPP prospective cohort study									
UCL COVID-19 Social Study	Trajectories of anxiety and depressive symptoms during enforced isolation due to COVID-19 in England: a longitudinal observational study	2021	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	36520	general population (geographic region)	all ages	monthly or more	continous follow-ups	0.5 year
UK Biobank (UKB)	Examining the association between family status and depression in the UK Biobank	2021	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	study = 150000	general population (geographic region)	>18 years	more than 5 years	single follow-up	8.7 years
Survey of Health, Ageing, and Retirement in Europe (SHARE)	Depressive symptoms and cognitive impairment: A 10-year follow-up study from the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe	2021	Multi center cohort study + age-based cohort study	Europe	study = 14231	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	11 years
English Longitudinal Study of Ageing (ELSA) Japan Gerontological Evaluation Study (JAGES)	Association between social isolation and depression onset among older adults: across-national longitudinal study in England and Japan	2021	Multi-cohort study + age-related study	United Kingdom	study UK = 3331 study Japan = 33127	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	single follow-up	2 years
Netherlands Study of Depression and Anxiety (NESDA), Netherlands Study of Depression in Older Persons (NESDO), and Netherlands Obsessive Compulsive Disorder Association Study (NOCDA).	The mental health impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on people with and without depressive, anxiety, or obsessive-compulsive disorders: a longitudinal study of three Dutch case-control cohorts.	2021	general prospective cohort study	Netherlands	1517	general population (geographic region)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	10+ years (baseline pre-pandemic data from 2006–2016; pandemic follow-up in 2020).

Youth in Iceland Study.	Depressive symptoms, mental wellbeing, and substance use among adolescents before and during the COVID-19 pandemic in Iceland: a longitudinal, population-based study.	2021	general prospective cohort study	Iceland	59701	general population (age-specific group(s))	<18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	4 years
UK Biobank	Impact of replacing sedentary behaviour with other movement behaviours on depression and anxiety symptoms: a prospective cohort study in the UK Biobank	2021	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	60235	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	2 years
Danish Blood Donor Study (DBDS)	The impact of health-related quality of life and depressive symptoms on blood donor career— Results from the Danish blood donor study	2021	general prospective cohort study	Denmark	102065	general population (geographic region)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	8 years
The Maastricht Study	Association of Retinal Nerve Fiber Layer Thickness, an Index of Neurodegeneration, With Depressive Symptoms Over Time	2021	general prospective cohort study	Netherlands	4934	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	from 1 to 6 months	multiple follow-ups	5 years (median)
Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children (ALSPAC)	The cross-sectional and longitudinal relationship between overgeneral autobiographical memory and adolescent depression in a UK population-based cohort	2021	birth or age-based cohort study	United Kingdom	4111	general population (age-specific group(s))	<18 years	from 1 to 6 months	multiple follow-ups	4 years

UK Biobank	Muscle strength and incidence of depression and anxiety: findings from the UK Biobank prospective cohort study	2022	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	162167	general population (country representative)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	8
SHARE (Survey of Health, Ageing, Retirement in Europe)	Variation in depressive symptom trajectories in a large sample of couples	2022	multi-center cohort study	Europe	22272	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	12 years
Millenium Cohort Study, Next Steps, British Cohort, National Child Development	Predictors of longer-term depression trajectories during the COVID-19 pandemic: a longitudinal study in four UK cohorts	2022	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	16978	general population (age-specific group(s))	all ages	Depending on a cohort	multiple follow-ups	1 year
Health and Social Support Study (HeSSup) cohort	Residential greenness and risks of depression: Longitudinal associations with different greenness indicators and spatial scales in a Finnish population cohort	2022	general prospective cohort study	Finland	cohort = 24057 Study = 19851	general population (country representative)	>18 years	more than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	14 years
UK Biobank (UKB)	Structural neuroimaging measures and lifetime depression across levels of phenotyping in UK biobank	2022	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	study = 39300	general population (geographic region)	>18 years		cross-sectional	
Next Stop: Mum of the postpartum depression prevention (PPD) strategy in Poland	'Next Stop: Mum': Evaluation of a Postpartum Depression Prevention Strategy in Poland	2022	retrospectively constructed prospective cohort study	Poland	11238	general population (gender-specific group(s))	all ages	from 1 to 6 months	multiple follow-ups	10 months
Integrative Psychiatric Research (iPSYCH) Consortium	Deep Learning for Cross-Diagnostic Prediction of Mental Disorder Diagnosis and Prognosis Using Danish	2022	Case-cohort study + there are no questionnaires/interviews.	Denmark	63535	health system/insurance enrollees	all ages	irregular/as needed	continous follow-ups	35 years

	Nationwide Register and Genetic Data		National registry and blood samples for DNA							
Disease Analyzer Database (IQVIA) = 11 German health practices	No significant association between COVID-19 diagnosis and the incidence of depression and anxiety disorder? A retrospective cohort study conducted in Germany	2022	retrospectively constructed prospective cohort study	Germany	study = 56350	disease registries	>18 years		cross-sectional	
Helsinki Birth Cohort Study	Depressive symptoms and mortality-findings from Helsinki birth cohort study	2022	birth or age-based cohort study	Finland	cohort = 13345 study = 1955	general population (geographic region)	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	14.1 years
Coordinated analyses of 11 UK longitudinal studies (Millennium Cohort Study, ALSPAC, Next Steps, BCS70, NCDS, NSHD, USOC, ELSA, Generation Scotland, TwinsUK, Born in Bradford).	Psychological Distress Before and During the COVID-19 Pandemic Among Adults in the United Kingdom Based on Coordinated An	2022	multi-center cohort study	United Kingdom	49993	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	from 7 to 12 months	multiple follow-ups	1 year
Longitudinal study on immigrants in Greece	Adverse working conditions and immigrants' physical health and depression outcomes: a longitudinal study in Greece	2022	general prospective cohort study	Greece	308	general population (geographic region)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	2 years
NA	Self-rated health as a predictor of hospitalizations in patients with bipolar disorder or major depressive disorder:	2023	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	29966	general population (country representative)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	single follow-up	2 years

	A prospective cohort study of the UK Biobank									
Gutenberg Health Study (GHS)	The association of depressive symptoms and body weight change in midlife – Results from the Gutenberg Health Study in Germany	2023	population-based, prospective, observational single-center cohort study	Germany	12220	general population (country representative)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	single follow-up	5 years
NA	Narcissistic dimensions and depressive symptoms in patients across mental disorders in cognitive behavioural therapy and in psychoanalytic interactional therapy in Germany: a prospective cohort study	2023	general prospective cohort study	Germany	2371	general population (country representative)	>18 years			
CoLaus PsyCoLaus	Stability of the Subtypes of Major Depressive Disorder in Older Adults and the Influence of Mild Cognitive Impairment on the Stability	2023	general prospective cohort study	Switzerland	1888	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	irregular/as needed	multiple follow-ups	13 years
Nord Trondelag Health Study (HUNT)	Using the Triangle of Human Ecology for understanding self-rated depression: a quantitative study based on the HUNT 3 cohort	2023	retrospectively constructed prospective cohort study	Norway	40466	general population (geographic region)	>18 years		cross-sectional	
UK Biobank	Genetic risk, muscle strength and risk of incident major depressive	2023	General prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	345621	general population (country representative)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	single follow-up	8

	disorder: results from the UK Biobank									
Danish National Birth Cohort (DNBC)	Mode of birth and long-term maternal mental health: A follow-up study in the Danish National Birth Cohort	2023	birth or age-based cohort study	Denmark	42872	general population (country representative)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	11
UK Biobank (UKB)	Long-Term Air Pollution, Genetic Susceptibility, and the Risk of Depression and Anxiety: A Prospective Study in the UK Biobank Cohort	2023	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	398241	general population (geographic region)	>18 years	more than 5 years	single follow-up	8.7 years
Survey of Health, Ageing, and Retirement in Europe (SHARE)	The role of social deprivation and depression in dementia risk: findings from the longitudinal survey of health, ageing and retirement in Europe	2023	Multi center cohort study + age-based cohort study	Europe	Study = 11623	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	11 years
The Irish Longitudinal Study on Aging (TILDA)	Trajectories of generalized anxiety disorder, major depression and change in quality of life in adults aged 50 + : findings from a longitudinal analysis using representative, population-based data from Ireland	2023	birth or age-based cohort study	Ireland	6400	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	single follow-up	2 years
UK Biobank (UKB)	Individual and joint associations of anxiety disorder and depression with cardiovascular	2023	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	cohort = 502413 study = 431973	general population (geographic region)	>18 years		cross-sectional	

	disease: A UK Biobank prospective cohort study									
Lifelines	Work- and mental health-related events and body mass index trajectories during the Covid-19 lockdown. Evidence from the lifelines cohort study in the Netherlands	2023	general prospective cohort study	Netherlands	cohort = 167729 study = 64630	general population (geographic region)	>18 years	monthly or more	continuous follow-ups	1 year + 4 months
Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE).	Association between pain intensity and depressive symptoms in community-dwelling adults: longitudinal findings from the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE)	2023	exposure-specific cohort study	Europe	28515	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	single follow-up	2 years
Lifelines Cohort Study.	Do influence at work and possibilities for development mitigate the impact of job demands for workers with and without depression.	2023	general prospective cohort study	Netherlands	55950	general population (country representative)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	2 years
COVCO-Basel Cohort.	Depression trajectories during the COVID-19 pandemic in the high-quality health care setting of Switzerland: the COVCO-Basel cohort.	2023	general prospective cohort study	Switzerland	6396	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	monthly or more	multiple follow-ups	18 months

UK Biobank	Association of sugar intake from different sources with incident depression in the UK Biobank	2023	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	188426	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	12.3 years (mean)
Million Women Study	Depression, anxiety, psychotropic drugs, and acute myocardial infarction: large prospective study of United Kingdom women	2023	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	690335	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	13.9 years
China Health and Retirement Longitudinal Study (CHARLS), Health and Retirement Study (HRS), Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE)	Spousal concordance in adverse childhood experiences and the association with depressive symptoms in middle-aged and older adults: findings across China, the US, and Europe	2023	general prospective cohort study	Europe	CHARLS: 2,394 couples; HRS: 3,131 couples; SHARE: 1,831 couples	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 10 years	continuous follow-ups	
UK Biobank	Trends in incident diagnoses and drug prescriptions for anxiety and depression during the COVID-19 pandemic: an 18-month follow-up study based on the UK Biobank	2023	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	308400	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	from 7 to 12 months	multiple follow-ups	1.5 years
GESIS panel study, Swiss Household panel study	Trajectories of depressive symptoms and subjective well-being before and after the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic: Two six-year longitudinal studies	2024	cross-national, longitudinal study							

Data from the United Kingdom Household Longitudinal Study	Mental health disparities across sexual orientations during the COVID-19 pandemic: Longitudinal analysis of a UK nationally representative cohort	2024	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	32326	general population (country representative)	all ages		single follow-up	NA
data from English Longitudinal Study of Ageing (ELSA) and Health and Retirement Study (HRS)	Bidirectional relationship between chronic pain and depressive symptoms in middle-aged and older adults	2024	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	29860	general population (country representative)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	12 years
Interaction of Gene and Environment of Depression during PostPartum Cohort (IGEDEPP)	Modeling longitudinal relationships between sleep disturbances and depressed mood in postpartum: A cross-lagged panel design	2024	retrospectively constructed prospective cohort study	France	3310	general population (gender-specific group(s))	all ages	irregular/as needed	multiple follow-ups	1 year
Adult Psychiatric Morbidity Survey	Personality traits and change in depression status at 18 months: Findings from a British Psychiatric Morbidity Survey	2024	retrospectively constructed prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	2366	high-risk individuals	all ages	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	single follow-up	18 months
UK Biobank	The joint associations of physical activity and ultra-processed food consumption with depression: A cohort study in the UK Biobank	2024	retrospectively constructed prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	99126	general population (country representative)	>18 years	irregular/as needed	single follow-up	average of 12.1 years
Work Environment and Health in Denmark survey (WEHD)	Leadership at work and risk of treatment for depressive and anxiety disorders in Denmark. A nationwide	2024	retrospectively constructed prospective cohort study	Denmark	59743	occupational groups	all ages	from 1 to 6 months	multiple follow-ups	2 years

	prospective study with register-based follow up									
SHARE (Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe)	Sensory impairments and depressive symptoms in Europe: a cross-national cohort study	2024	multi-center cohort study	Europe	56847	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	7
Millennium Cohort Study	Longitudinal pathways between childhood BMI, body dissatisfaction, and adolescent depression: an observational study using the UK Millennium Cohort Study	2024	birth or age-based cohort study	United Kingdom	13135	general population (country representative)	<18 years	more than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	
ALSPAC (Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children), Millennium Cohort Study (MCS), Environmental Risk (E-Risk) Longitudinal Twin Study	The relationship between type, timing and duration of exposure to adverse childhood experiences and adolescent self-harm and depression: findings from three UK prospective population-based cohorts	2024	birth or age-based cohort study	United Kingdom	22000	general population (age-specific group(s))	all ages	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	
Hellenic Longitudinal Investigation of Aging and Diet (HELIAD)	Depressive symptoms in the entire spectrum of cognitive ageing in Greece: evidence from the Hellenic Longitudinal Investigation of Aging and Diet (HELIAD)	2024	general prospective cohort study	Greece	1936	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	irregular/as needed	multiple follow-ups	7 years
Genetic Risk and Outcome in Psychosis (GROUP), Dutch Bipolar Cohort (DBC), NESDA	Childhood abuse v. neglect and risk for major psychiatric disorders	2024	disease-oriented cohort study	Netherlands	4037	patients with a specific symptom	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	Varies by cohort

Lifelines Cohort Study	Educational inequalities in major depressive disorder prevalence	2024	general prospective cohort study	Netherlands	167729	general population (country representative)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	18 years
Hamburg City Health Study (HCHS)	The differential role of socioeconomic status dimensions in depressive symptoms of aging adults: data from the Hamburg City Health cohort Study	2024	general prospective cohort study	Germany	8400	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years		multiple follow-ups	6 years
German National Cohort (NAKO)	Mental health of individuals with pre-existing mental illnesses at the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic: results of the German National Cohort (NAKO)	2024	multi-center cohort study	Germany	135445	general population (geographic region)	all ages	irregular/as needed	multiple follow-ups	5 years
ELSA	The reciprocal associations between social deficits, social engagement, and inflammation: Longitudinal evidence comparing venous blood samples and dried blood spots and mapping the modifying role of phenotypic and genotypic depression	2024	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	10290	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	14 years
UK Biobank	Depression and severe non-alcoholic fatty liver disease	2024	nested case-control study	United Kingdom	481181	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	13.5

The Older Persons and Informal Caregivers Survey Minimal Data Set (TOPICS-MDS)	Longitudinal associations between subjective cognitive impairment, pain and depressive symptoms in home-dwelling older adults: Modelling within-person effects	2024	general prospective cohort study	Netherlands	cohort = 46456 study = 11582	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	from 1 to 6 months	multiple follow-ups	1 year
Survey of Health, Ageing, and Retirement in Europe (SHARE)	Association between depression and incident dementia: Longitudinal findings from the share study	2024	Multi center cohort study + age-based cohort study	Europe	study = 22789	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	16 years
(no cohort name, extraction of prescription, clinical, and socio-demographic records from national databases)	Depression Treatment Trajectories and Associated Social Determinants: A Three-Year Follow-Up Study in 66,540 Older Adults Undergoing First-Time Depression Treatment in Denmark	2024	National registry data, no questionnaires	Denmark	66540	Age specific + patients undergoing a specific treatment + medical records enrollees	>18 years	from 1 to 6 months	multiple follow-ups	3 years
UK Biobank (UKB)	Associations between oral health and depression and anxiety: A cross-sectional and prospective cohort study from the UK Biobank	2024	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	305188	general population (geographic region)	>18 years		cross-sectional	
the Adolescent Brain and Cognitive Development (ABCD) = North American Avon Longitudinal Study of Parents and Children (ALSPAC) = United Kingdom	Genetic Architectures of Adolescent Depression Trajectories in 2 Longitudinal Population Cohorts	2024	multi-center cohort study	United Kingdom	ABCD = 11876 ALSPAC = 15645	patients with a specific disease (ABCD) + birth cohort (ALSPAC)	<18 years	irregular/as needed	multiple follow-ups	6 years

the Lundbeck Foundation Initiative for Integrative Psychiatric Research (iPSYCH)	Population-Based Risk of Psychiatric Disorders Associated With Recurrent Copy Number Variants	2024	Case-cohort study + there are no questionnaires/interviews. National registry and blood samples for DNA	Denmark	study= 92531	health system/insurance enrollees	all ages	irregular/as needed	continous follow-ups	35 years
China Health and Retirement Longitudinal Study (CHARLS) = China Survey of Health, Ageing, and Retirement in Europe (SHARE) = Europe	The influence of residential Environment and residential experience on psychological depression in older adults: Evidence from China and Europe	2024	Exposure specific + age specific	Europe	China = 11026 Europe = 13485	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years		cross-sectional	
UK Biobank (UKB)	Adherence to the EAT-Lancet diet and incident depression and anxiety	2024	exposure-specific cohort study	United Kingdom	study = 180446	general population (geographic region)	>18 years	from 1 to 6 months	multiple follow-ups	1 year
English Longitudinal Study of Ageing (ELSA) Study of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE) National Health and Ageing Trends Study (NHATS)	Association Between Dementia, Change in Home-Care Use, and Depressive Symptoms During the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Longitudinal Study Using Data from Three Cohort Studies	2024	Multi-cohort study + age-related study	Europe	study = 43475	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	irregular/as needed	multiple follow-ups	1.5 years
UK Biobank.	Replacement of sedentary behavior with various physical activities and the risk of incident depression: a prospective analysis of accelerometer-measured and self-reported UK Biobank data.	2024	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	84168	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	12.21 years (mean follow-up duation)

UK Biobank	The association of early life factors with depression and anxiety in adults aged 40–69 years: a population-based cohort study	2024	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	502394	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 10 years	multiple follow-ups	13.6 years (median)
Seguimiento Universidad de Navarra (SUN) Project	Predicted vitamin D levels and risk of depression in the SUN Project: A prospective cohort study	2024	general prospective cohort study	Spain	18746	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	4 years
Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort Study (MoBa)	Wellbeing and illbeing in women exposed to physical and sexual violence during peripregnancy: A population-based longitudinal study	2024	general prospective cohort study	Norway	74947	Pregnant Women	>18 years	from 7 to 12 months	multiple follow-ups	3 years
UK Biobank	Influence of cognitive reserve on risk of depression and subsequent dementia: A large community-based longitudinal study	2024	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	436232	general population (country representative)	>18 years	more than 10 years	multiple follow-ups	12.96 years

Table 11 – Data extraction results from studies using clinical cohorts in depression.

Name of Cohort Study	Title of manuscript	Year of publication	Study Design	Country	Sample size	Type of population	Age range of population	Frequency of follow-up	Number of follow-ups	Total Duration
----------------------	---------------------	---------------------	--------------	---------	-------------	--------------------	-------------------------	------------------------	----------------------	----------------

										of follow-up
Data were obtained from the Netherlands Study of Depression and Anxiety (NESDA)	Personality traits and the risk of incident (hypo)mania among subjects initially suffering from depressive and anxiety disorders in a 9-year cohort study	2019	general prospective cohort study	Netherlands	2981	general population (country representative)	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	9 years
Netherlands Study of Depression and Anxiety (NESDA)	Biomarker-based subtyping of depression and anxiety disorders using Latent Class Analysis. A NESDA study	2019	disease-oriented cohort study	Netherlands	1460	patients with a specific symptom	>18 years	irregular/as needed	multiple follow-ups	1
Netherlands Study of Depression and Anxiety (NESDA)	Longitudinal predictors for suicide attempts in major depressive disorder	2019	disease-oriented cohort study	Netherlands	1713	patients with a specific symptom	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	6 years
The Netherlands Study of Depression and Anxiety (NESDA)	Anxiety sensitivity, its stability and longitudinal association with severity of anxiety symptoms	2019	disease-oriented cohort study	Netherlands	cohort = 2981 study = 2052	General population + patients with specific symptoms + high risk individuals	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	single follow-up	2 years
Netherlands Study of Depression and Anxiety (NESDA)	The association of depression and anxiety with cardiac autonomic activity: The role of confounding effects of antidepressants	2019	disease-oriented cohort study	Netherlands	2981	patients with specific disease	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	9 years
Netherlands Study of Depression and Anxiety (NESDA)	Stability of chronotype over a 7-year follow-up period and its association with severity of depressive and anxiety symptoms	2020	disease-oriented cohort study	Netherlands	1417	patients with specific disease	>18 years	from 7 to 12 months	multiple follow-ups	7 years
The Netherlands Study of Depression and Anxiety (NESDA)	Depression profilers and immunometabolic dysregulation: Longitudinal results from the NESDA study	2020	exposure-specific cohort study	Netherlands	study = 2882	General population (geographic) + disease-specific	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	6 years

Netherlands Study of Depression and Anxiety (NESDA)	Anger and cluster B personality traits and the conversion from unipolar depression to bipolar disorder	2020	disease-oriented cohort study	Netherlands	cohort = 2981 study = 1585	General population (geographic) + disease-specific	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	9 years
Netherlands Study of Depression and Anxiety (NESDA)	Bidirectional longitudinal associations of omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acid plasma levels with depressive disorders	2020	general prospective cohort study	Netherlands	2912	patients with specific disease	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	6 years
data from the large cohort study of the Netherlands Study of Depression and Anxiety (NESDA)	Chronotype changes with age; seven-year follow-up from the Netherlands study of depression and anxiety cohort	2021	Data from the multi-center (Groningen, Amsterdam, Leiden) NESDA cohort study was used	Netherlands	2981	general population (country representative)	>18 years	more than 5 years	single follow-up	7 years
Netherlands Study of Depression and Anxiety (NESDA)	Cohort profile of the longitudinal Netherlands Study of Depression and Anxiety (NESDA) on etiology, course and consequences of depressive and anxiety disorders.	2021	general prospective cohort study	Netherlands	3348	patients with specific disease	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	13+ years
Netherlands Study of Depression and Anxiety (NESDA)	Temporal relationships between happiness and psychiatric disorders and their symptom severity in a large cohort study	2021	general prospective cohort study	Netherlands	1816	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	3 years
The Netherlands Study of Depression and Anxiety (NESDA)	Childhood trauma and its impact on depressive and anxiety symptomatology in adulthood: A 6-year longitudinal study	2022	exposure-specific cohort study	Netherlands	cohort = 2981 study = 1803	General population (geographic) + disease-specific	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	6 years
COVID-19 Psychiatry and Neurological Genetics study (COPING) and (2) the Repeated Assessment of Mental Health in Pandemics (RAMP)	Depression, anxiety and PTSD symptoms before and during the COVID-19 pandemic in the UK	2023	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	12718	general population (country representative)	all ages	irregular/as needed	single follow-up	2 years

Table 12 – Data extraction results from studies using population cohorts in AD and other dementias.

Name of Cohort Study	Title of manuscript	Year of publication	Study Design	Country	Sample size	Type of population	Age range of population	Frequency of follow-up	Number of follow-ups	Total Duration of follow-up
UK Biobank	Reserve and Alzheimer's disease genetic risk: Effects on hospitalization and mortality	2019	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	242958	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	follow-up period up to 10 years (average 5 7.58 years).
UK Biobank	Predicting incident dementia 3-8 years after brief cognitive tests in the UK Biobank prospective study of 500,000 people	2019	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	385336	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	5.2 median years
Copenhagen General Population Study (CGPS) and Copenhagen City Heart Study (CCHS)	Blood-brain barrier transcytosis genes, risk of dementia and stroke: a prospective cohort study of 74,754 individuals	2019	general prospective cohort study	Denmark	74754	general population (country representative)	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	median follow-up of 10 years (range 0–25 years)
Amyloid Imaging to Prevent Alzheimer's Disease (AMYPAD) Prognostic and Natural History Study (PNHS)	Quantitative amyloid PET in Alzheimer's disease: the AMYPAD prognostic and natural history study	2019	prospective multi-center	Europe	up to 2000 subjects	high-risk individuals	>18 years	from 7 to 12 months	multiple follow-ups	At least 12 months
Copenhagen General Population Study	APOE and dementia – resequencing and	2020	general prospective cohort study	Denmark	105597	general population (country representative)	>18 years	irregular/as needed	multiple follow-ups	median follow-up of 40 years

(CGPS) and Copenhagen City Heart Study (CCHS)	genotyping in 105,597 individuals									(range 0 to 41 years)
Swedish Twin Registry	A Twin Study of Sex Differences in Genetic Risk for All Dementia, Alzheimer's Disease (AD), and Non-AD Dementia	2020	Co-twin analysis	Sweden	13559 individual twins	twin population	>18 years	irregular/as needed	multiple follow-ups	2–5 years following the first twin's diagnosis
UK Biobank	Lower serum testosterone concentrations are associated with a higher incidence of dementia in men: The UK Biobank prospective cohort study	2021	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	159411 men	general population (country representative)	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	7 years, median follow-up of 7.03 years (interquartile range, IQR: 6.32-7.73)
English Longitudinal Study of Ageing (ELSA), Whitehall II study	Sex differences and the role of education in cognitive ageing: analysis of two UK-based prospective cohort studies	2021	birth or age-based cohort study	United Kingdom	15924	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	13 years
European Prospective Investigation into Cancer and Nutrition (EPIC)-Spain Dementia Cohort Study	Mediterranean Diet and Risk of Dementia and Alzheimer's Disease in the EPIC-Spain Dementia Cohort Study	2021	general prospective cohort study	Spain	16160	general population (geographic region)	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	21.6 (±3.4)-year mean follow-up time
UK Biobank	Associations Between Handgrip Strength and Dementia Risk, Cognition, and Neuroimaging Outcomes in the UK Biobank Cohort Study	2022	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	190406	general population (country representative)	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	median (IQR) follow-up of 11.7 (11.0-12.4) years

UK Biobank	Body mass index, genetic susceptibility, and Alzheimer's disease: a longitudinal study based on 475,813 participants from the UK Biobank	2022	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	475813	general population (country representative)	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	11.58-year mean follow-up time
UK Biobank	Macronutrient Intake and Risk of Dementia in Community-Dwelling Older Adults: A Nine-Year Follow-Up Cohort Study	2022	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	93389	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	8.7(interquartile range= 8.6–9.4)-year median follow-up time
UK Biobank	Tea consumption and risk of incident dementia: A prospective cohort study of 377 592 UK Biobank participants	2022	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	417085	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	9.09(interquartile range=7.08–10.64)-year median follow-up time
UK Biobank	Associations of resting heart rate with incident dementia, cognition, and brain structure: a prospective cohort study of UK biobank	2022	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	339901	general population (country representative)	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	3148(±941.08)-day mean follow-up time
UK Biobank	Neighbourhood residential density, urbanicity and incident dementia and Alzheimer's disease: A 12-year prospective cohort study from the UK Biobank	2023	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	239629	general population (age-specific group(s))	<18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	median follow-up of 12.3 years (interquartile range 11.5–13.0 years)
UK Biobank	A Phenome-wide Association and Mendelian Randomization Study for Alzheimer's Disease: A Prospective Cohort Study of	2023	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	502493	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	13 years

	502,493 Participants From the UK Biobank									
UK Biobank	Prediction Abilities of SCORE2 Risk Algorithms for Incident Dementia and All-Cause Mortality: Results From the UK Biobank Cohort Study	2023	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	429033	general population (country representative)	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	median follow-up of 12.8 years
UK Biobank	The association of night shift work with the risk of all-cause dementia and Alzheimer's disease: a longitudinal study of 245,570 UK Biobank participants	2023	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	245570	ethnic/racial groups	>18 years		multiple follow-ups	13,1-year mean follow-up time
UK Biobank	Associations of screen-based sedentary activities with all cause dementia, Alzheimer's disease, vascular dementia: a longitudinal study based on 462,524 participants from the UK Biobank	2023	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	462524	general population (country representative)	>18 years	irregular/as needed		13.6-year median follow-up time
UK Biobank	Association of pro-inflammatory diet with increased risk of all-cause dementia and Alzheimer's dementia: a prospective study of 166,377 UK Biobank participants	2023	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	166377	general population (country representative)	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	9.46-year median follow-up time
Danish Nurses Cohort (DNC)	Depression in Mid- and Later-Life and Risk of Dementia in Women: A	2023	general prospective cohort study	Denmark	25651	occupational groups	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous	23-year average follow-up time

	Prospective Study within the Danish Nurses Cohort								follow-ups	
UK Biobank	Association Between Regular Laxative Use and Incident Dementia in UK Biobank Participants	2023	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	502229	general population (country representative)	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	9.8(±1.5)-year mean follow-up time
UK Biobank	The association between urinary sodium and the risk of dementia: Evidence from a population-based cohort study	2024	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	458577	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	13.6 years
UK Biobank	Unveiling the link between physical activity levels and dementia risk: Insights from the UK Biobank study	2024	retrospectively constructed prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	354123	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	median (interquartile range) follow-up time of 12.5 years (11.80 - 13.26 years)
UK Biobank	Associations between different coffee types, neurodegenerative diseases, and related mortality: findings from a large prospective cohort study	2024	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	204847	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	median follow-up period of 9 years
UK Biobank	Age at Onset of Heart Failure and Subsequent Risk of Dementia A Longitudinal Cohort Study	2024	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	457204	health system/insurance enrollees	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	median follow-up of 12.8 years
UK Biobank	Osteoarthritis, osteoarthritis treatment and risk of incident dementia: a	2024	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	466460	general population (country representative)	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	median follow-up of 11.90 (SD1.01) years

	prospective cohort study based on UK Biobank									
UK Biobank	Non-Linear Association of Dietary Polyamines with the Risk of Incident Dementia: Results from Population-Based Cohort of the UK Biobank	2024	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	77029	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	more than 1 year and less than 5 years	multiple follow-ups	12-year median follow-up time
UK Biobank	Total physical activity, plant-based diet and neurodegenerative diseases: A prospective cohort study of the UK biobank	2024	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	173311	general population (country representative)	>18 years	irregular/as needed	multiple follow-ups	3.86(±1.00)-year mean follow-up time
UK Biobank	Association of birthweight and risk of incident dementia: a prospective cohort study	2024	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	275648	general population (country representative)	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	13-year mean follow-up time
UK Biobank	Associations of sugar intake, high-sugar dietary pattern, and the risk of dementia: a prospective cohort study of 210,832 participants	2024	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	210832	general population (geographic region)	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	11.80 (±1.66)-year mean follow-up time
UK Biobank	Intrinsic Capacity, Polygenic Risk Score, APOE Genotype, and Risk of Dementia	2024	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	366406	general population (country representative)	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	13.5(interquartile range=12.8–14.2)-year median follow-up time

UK Biobank	Genetic influence on within-person longitudinal change in anthropometric traits in the UK Biobank	2024	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	50117	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	7.4-year average follow-up time
UK Biobank	Association of MAFLD and MASLD with all-cause and cause-specific dementia: a prospective cohort study	2024	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	403506	general population (country representative)	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	13.7(interquartile range =12.9–14.4)-year median follow-up time
UK Biobank	Serum urate levels and neurodegenerative outcomes: a prospective cohort study and mendelian randomization analysis of the UK Biobank	2024	general prospective cohort study	United Kingdom	382182	general population (country representative)	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continuous follow-ups	12-year median follow-up time

Table 13 – Data extraction results from studies using clinical cohorts in AD and other dementias.

Name of Cohort Study	Title of manuscript	Year of publication	Study Design	Country	Sample size	Type of population	Age range of population	Frequency of follow-up	Number of follow-ups	Total Duration of follow-up
the European Medical Information Framework for Alzheimer's Disease (EMIF-AD), Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative (ADNI), Amsterdam Dementia Cohort (ADC), and the Swedish BioFINDER study	Biomarker-based prognosis for people with mild cognitive impairment (ABIDE): a modelling study	2019	disease-oriented cohort study	Netherlands	2611	patients with specific disease	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continous follow-ups	mean follow-up of 3 years (SD 2)
Impact of Cholinergic Treatment Use (ICTUS) study	Potentially modifiable factors associated with agitation and aggression in Alzheimer's disease: results of the ICTUS study	2019	disease-oriented cohort study	France	1375	patients with specific disease	>18 years	from 1 to 6 months	multiple follow-ups	2 years
European Prevention of Alzheimer's Dementia (EPAD)	European Prevention of Alzheimer's Dementia Longitudinal Cohort Study (EPAD LCS): study protocol	2019	prospective multi-center	Europe	several thousand people	general population (age-specific group(s))	>18 years	from 1 to 6 months	multiple follow-ups	> 4 years
GERAS	Determinants of time to institutionalisation and related healthcare and societal costs in a	2019	disease-oriented cohort study	Europe	1495	patients with specific disease	>18 years	from 1 to 6 months	multiple follow-ups	18 months in UK and 36 months in

	community-based cohort of patients with Alzheimer's disease dementia									France and Germany
Amsterdam Dementia Cohort	Orthostatic Hypotension: An Important Risk Factor for Clinical Progression to Mild Cognitive Impairment or Dementia. The Amsterdam Dementia Cohort	2019	disease-oriented cohort study	Netherlands	1882	patients with specific disease	>18 years	irregular/as needed	continous follow-ups	2.2 (±1.4)-year mean follow-up time
Impact of Cholinergic Treatment Use (ICTUS) study	Antidepressant Use and Progression of Mild to Moderate Alzheimer's Disease: Results from the European ICTUS Cohort	2020	prospective multi-center	France	587	patients with specific disease	>18 years	from 1 to 6 months	multiple follow-ups	2 years
Swedish Dementia Registry (SveDem) and Swedish Population Register (NPR)	Increased risk of epilepsy in patients registered in the Swedish Dementia Registry	2020	cross-sectional	Sweden	305125 (81192 SveDem + 223933 controls)	health system/insurance enrollees	>18 years	from 7 to 12 months	continous follow-ups	The risk of epilepsy 5 and 10 years after dementia diagnosis was estimated with Kaplan-Meier curves, and Cox proportional hazard modelling was used to identify risk factors and adjust for comorbidities

MEMENTO cohort	Diabetes Mellitus and Cognition Pathway Analysis in the MEMENTO Cohort	2021	cross-sectional	France	2288	patients with a specific symptom	>18 years		cross-sectional	no follow-up (association between diabetes mellitus and cognition by observing latent characteristics at baseline)
----------------	--	------	-----------------	--------	------	----------------------------------	-----------	--	-----------------	--

Table 14 – Data extraction results from studies using clinical cohorts in endometriosis.

Name of Cohort Study	Title of manuscript	Year of publication	Study Design	Country	Sample size	Type of population	Age range of population	Frequency of follow-up	Number of follow-ups	Total Duration of follow-up
Visanne Post-approval Observational Study (VIPOS)	Risk of depression and anemia in users of hormonal endometriosis treatments: Results from the VIPOS study	2020	disease-oriented cohort study	Europe	27840	general population (gender-specific group(s))	all ages	from 7 to 12 months	continuous follow-ups	up to 84 months

